

PARLIAMENT
OF THE REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

REVIEW OF THE FIVE-YEAR TERM OF THE NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN 2030

**Focussing on the agriculture, rural development,
land reform, and fisheries sectors**

REVIEW OF THE FIVE-YEAR TERM OF THE NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN 2030

**A FOCUS ON THE AGRICULTURE, RURAL DEVELOPMENT,
LAND REFORM, AND FISHERIES SECTORS**

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

1H1HA	One Household, One Hectare
ADEP	Aquaculture Development and Enhancement Programme
APAP	Agricultural Policy Action Plan
CAADP	Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme
CRDP	Comprehensive Rural Development Programme
DAFF	Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries
DMR	Department of Mineral Resources
DOT	Department of Transport
DPME	Department of Planning, Monitoring and Evaluation
DRDLR	Department of Rural Development and Land Reform
EDD	Economic Development Department
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EPWP	Expanded Public Works Programme
FFC	Financial and Fiscal Commission
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
Ha(s)	Hectare/s
HDIs	Historically Disadvantaged Individuals
IFSS	Integrated Food Security Strategy
IPV	Inshore Patrol Vessels
IUU	Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated
LED	Local Economic Development
MDG	Millennium Development Goals
MLRA	Marine Living Resources Act
MPA	Marine Protected Areas
MTSF	Medium Term Strategic Framework
NAMC	National Agricultural Marketing Council
NARYSEC	National Rural Youth Service Corps
NDP	National Development Plan
NIP	National Infrastructure Plan
NMISA	National Metrology Institute of South Africa
NSDF	National Spatial Development Framework
NPC	National Planning Commission
PDALFA	Preservation and Development of Agricultural Land Framework
RADP	Recapitalisation and Development Programme
R&D	Research and Development
REID	Rural Enterprise and Industrial Development
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SMMEs	Small, Medium and Micro-sized Enterprises
SPLUMA	Spatial Planning and Land Use Management Act
TAC	Total Allowable Catch

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In August 2012, the South African Government adopted the National Development Plan (NDP) as the launchpad and blueprint for a future economic and socio-economic development strategy for the country. The NDP sets key priorities for the Government to eliminate poverty and reduce inequality by 2030 through a range of policy interventions. The NDP follows a holistic approach towards achieving its main goals, which cut across various departments. However, the focus of this paper is limited to the role of the then Departments of Rural Development and Land Reform (DRDLR); and Agriculture Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF),¹ as they are required to work together towards the attainment of the goals set out in Chapter 6 of the NDP, titled “inclusive rural economy”. Chapter 6 envisions rural areas that are spatially, socially and economically well integrated, where residents have economic growth, food security and jobs, as well as improved access to basic services, healthcare and public transport. It envisages that by 2030 Agriculture will create close to one million new jobs, contributing significantly to reducing overall unemployment.

The vision of the NDP is to be implemented in three phases over a five-year planning cycle, known as the Medium Term Strategic Framework (MTSF), which covers the periods 2014-2019, 2019-2024 and 2024-2029. This paper reviews progress on the implementation of Chapter 6 of the NDP over the five-year cycle of the 2014-2019 MTSF. The aim is to identify gaps and suggest measures that could be taken to ensure that the new Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development and the Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries, meet their NDP targets.

The 2014-2019 MTSF is structured around 14 priority Outcomes, which cover focus areas identified in the NDP. The then DRDLR, supported by DAFF, is specifically required to lead in the implementation of Outcome 7: Vibrant, equitable, sustainable rural communities contributing towards food security. Both departments also contribute towards Outcome 4: Decent employment through inclusive growth and Outcome 10: Protect and enhance our environmental assets and natural resources.

Over the 2014-2019 MTSF period, DAFF focused on improving food security and safety; creating jobs; increasing the contribution of the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sectors to Gross Domestic Product (GDP); and upgrading infrastructure. The agricultural sector has undergone major structural changes that were mainly driven by drought, under-investment, plant and animal pests and diseases, stringent sanitary and phyto-sanitary protocols from trade partners, as well as other macro-economic factors that constrained growth and development of the sector. As a result, the agricultural sector’s contribution to the GDP has shrunk and it has shed jobs, despite the NDP setting it at the forefront of job creation. Further, although the expansion of small-scale production in agriculture, forestry and fisheries is essential to creating a dynamic inclusive, rural economy in former homeland areas, Government did not achieve its target to have 300 000 new smallholders (producing for market) by 2019 over the 2014-2019 MTSF period.

In terms of food security, South Africa’s rural strategy aimed at strengthening food security and agricultural competitiveness while lifting marginalised rural households, especially in former homeland areas, out of poverty, made some positive impact. However, chronic under-development with its social, economic and cultural dimensions still continues in many rural areas. To transform the rural economy, investment is required in infrastructure, services, skills and productivity. Other recommendations aimed at ensuring that Government is on the right track to deliver on its NDP targets include encouraging expansion

¹ Departments were re-configured following the national general elections in 2019.

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in labour-intensive agricultural commodities; and tailor-made support packages for targeted market-oriented smallholder farmers in an expanded land reform, which is key in creating large numbers of new employment opportunities.

In the rural development and land reform sector, Government reports poor progress in the implementation of the NDP during the 2014-2019 MTSF period through the six priorities of Outcome 7. The Department of Performance Monitoring and Evaluation (DPME) reports that of 39 targets, Government only managed to achieve 18 (46%), while 19 (49%) were not achieved and two (5%) were not reported on. The DRDLR did not achieve the major target of addressing inequality in land ownership and unemployment in rural areas. For example, it did not meet the target of transferring two million hectares of productive land ownership to Previously Disadvantaged Individuals (PDIs) by 2019. Instead, only 1.012 million hectares were acquired, translating into 50% achievement of the target. The Department also did not manage to achieve the target of employing 934 140 rural people through rural development and land reform initiatives by 2019. Instead, 622 946 rural people were employed through initiatives such as the Comprehensive Rural Development Programme (CRDP), National Rural Youth Service Corps (NARYSEC), Agri-Parks and others.

In terms of the priority on food security and poverty alleviation, improvements have been recorded. The percentage of households and the number of people vulnerable to hunger has decreased between 2011 and 2018. However, the decline was driven by widespread access to social grants provided by the Department of Social Development rather than initiatives by the DRDLR. This notwithstanding, Government reports substantial improvement in ensuring access to diverse and affordable food in rural areas. However, despite the decline in vulnerability to hunger of South Africans, a large percentage of households (21%) continue to experience difficulty to access food. Of those with inadequate access to food, 25.5% comprise rural households.

Noteworthy, the DRDLR exceeded its target of supporting 4.3 million people vulnerable to hunger (which translates into 1.6 million households by 2019), as it was able to support 6.7 million people that were vulnerable to hunger (which translates into 2.6 million households). Despite substantial investment in addressing backlogs in water, sanitation and electricity service delivery in rural areas, the delivery of these services continue to lag behind national norms. This means much still needs to be done in clearing the backlogs in key services, such as water, sanitation, electricity, roads, education and health, which are significantly worse in rural than in urban areas. There is also a need to intensify the political will to reduce poverty and unemployment in rural areas and ensure various departments fast-track the implementation of the NDP, especially chapter six, which deals with agriculture, land reform and rural development. This includes fast tracking the pace of acquiring land for PDIs in line with the NDP. In particular, there is a need to review the role and function of the Office of the Valuer-General, which is meant to assist in accelerating land reform. Further, the processing of a legislative framework to allow for expropriation of land without compensation needs to be finalised.

The fisheries sector in South Africa is globally recognised for its marine production and management. The contribution of the sector to an integrated and inclusive rural economy could be advanced to transform the historical patterns of ownership and economic participation. The Department had undertaken to review and comprehensively amend the Marine Living Resources Act (MLRA), No. 18 of 1998, to address observed weaknesses in the transformation of fisheries, such as fronting and armchair fishers. This legislative review did not take place during the 2014-2019 MTSF period. Targeted fisheries research should be pursued, together with viable fishing rights allocation and sustainable exploitation of

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fisheries resources. The NDP cautions against issuing many fishing rights of low value, as it lowers the average gain per fisher and could be ineffective in fighting poverty, food insecurity and non-compliance among fishers. The former responded to the NDP's call through various means. Some discussion focused on reorganising commercial fishing rights allocations to accommodate small-scale fishers while bearing in mind the perceived threats to jobs. There is also a need to intensify fisheries research and active monitoring systems are considered of paramount importance to ensure a viable and sustainable fishery.

However, this has proven to be a challenge. In most coastal and fishing communities, the creation or advancement of alternative economic opportunities was not available to supplement livelihoods of fishing communities. Since small-scale fishing rights were not allocated during the 2014-2019 period, there is no positive outcome on employment and sustainable rural communities contributing towards food security for all. Due to porous harbours and weak implementation of fisheries research and law enforcement, there is minimal improvement in the protection and enhancement of environmental assets and natural resources.

There are still opportunities to advance rural economic development through aquaculture. The aquaculture sector has high growth potential due to increasing demand for fish in the face of declining fish stocks in the ocean and South Africa's abundance of marine and freshwater resources. Parliament should improve its oversight role to ensure that more effort is diverted towards fisheries research and development, and active monitoring systems to provide a viable and sustainable fishery. Furthermore, Parliament should receive regular reports and conduct oversight visits to programmes and projects on alternative economic opportunities needed to supplement livelihoods of fishing communities, such as agro-processing, tourism, fisheries and small enterprises, where the potential exists.

Though progress has been made towards realising the goals of the NDP 2030 across the economic services, social services and governance, progress is uneven across sectors. Furthermore, performance on NDP 2030 actions, which require cooperation across multiple departments, spheres of government or non-governmental stakeholders, shows poor implementation progress. The slow/poor implementation of the NDP could be ascribed to the fact that there are too many Government priorities that are accorded equal weighting and status. As a result, resources are thinly spread, considering the current economic environment. Inadequate information systems in Government to track progress towards achievement of the Vision of the NDP 2030 is also identified as a key challenge.

1. INTRODUCTION

In August 2012, the South African Government adopted the National Development Plan (NDP) as the launchpad and blueprint for a future economic and socio-economic development strategy for the country. The core priorities of the NDP are to eliminate poverty; reduce inequality and unemployment through inclusive economic growth; build human capabilities so to enable people to lead lives they value; enhance the capacity of the State; and promote leadership and active citizenship throughout society.² In particular, the NDP commits the South African Government to **eradicating absolute poverty** by uplifting the 39% of citizens that live below the poverty line; **reducing the unemployment rate to 6%** by creating 11 million more jobs; and **significantly reducing inequality** from 0.69 to 0.60 Gini coefficient by 2030, through a range of policy interventions. The NDP offers a long-term perspective. It defines a desired destination and identifies the role different sectors of society need to play in reaching that goal. It is founded on six pillars that represent the broad objectives to eliminate poverty and reduce inequality by **2030** by:

- Uniting South Africans of all races and classes around a common programme to eliminate poverty and reduce inequality.
- Encouraging citizens to be active in their own development, in strengthening democracy and in holding their government accountable.
- Raising economic growth, promoting exports and making the economy more labour absorbing.
- Focusing on key capabilities of both people and the country. Capabilities include skills, infrastructure, social security, strong institutions and partnerships both within the country and with key international partners.
- Building a capable and developmental State.
- Building strong leadership throughout society that works together to solve problems.

As a long-term strategic plan, the NDP serves four broad objectives:

- Providing overarching goals for what the country wants to achieve by 2030.
- Building consensus on the key obstacles faced by South Africa and what needs to be done to overcome those obstacles.
- Providing a shared long-term strategic framework within which more detailed planning can take place in order to advance the long-term goals set out in the NDP.
- Creating a basis for making choices about how best to rationalise limited budgets and resources in the public sector.

The rationale underlying the development of such a long-term plan is the acknowledgement of the need for a coherent vision for the future, in order to realise changes in the socio-economic structure and the culture of society; which are a result of a history of oppression, exploitation and dispossession. The NDP envisions a South Africa where everyone feels free, yet bound to others; where everyone embraces their full potential; a country where opportunity is determined not by birth, but by ability, education and hard work. The NDP aims to ensure that all South Africans attain a decent standard of living through the elimination of poverty and reduction of inequality. The core elements of a decent standard of living identified in the Plan are:

- Housing, water, electricity and sanitation.
- Safe and reliable public transport.

² The Presidency (2019) e

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- Quality education and skills development.
- Safety and security.
- Quality health care.
- Social protection.
- Employment.
- Recreation and leisure.
- Clean environment.
- Adequate nutrition.

Achieving South Africa's vision for 2030 depends on the effective implementation of the NDP, and the country's ability to adapt and learn during this process. Implementing the Plan is the shared responsibility of Government, the private sector, civil society and individual citizens. The achievement of the NDP goals requires cooperative and integrated planning across national, provincial and local governments; the private sector; labour; and civil society. The three spheres of Government need to work collaboratively to ensure alignment between their powers and functions, the planning processes and budget allocation processes.

1.1 Implementation Modalities of the NDP

The Medium Term Strategic Framework (MTSF) is Government's five-year strategic plan for implementation of the NDP. The intention was to develop five-year plans towards the achievement of the 2030 Vision, aligned to the electoral cycles. The 2014-2019 MTSF was designed to identify critical actions to be undertaken during 2014 - 2019 that would put the country on a positive trajectory towards the achievement of the 2030 Vision. It set out indicators and targets to be achieved within the planning period. The aim was to, as far as possible, reflect department-specific NDP targets to enable direct links between the NDP, MTSF and departmental strategic and annual performance plans. The 2014-19 MTSF provided national strategic direction for the country's development over the medium term, considering the autonomy of provincial and local governments to do their own planning. The plan was intended to inform and guide the alignment of institutional plans in each sphere of government. The aim was to provide a clear outline of the priorities for the planning cycle and to also allow for necessary prioritisation of a few critical interventions and the sequencing of their implementation that enabled effective and optimal resource allocation. Concisely, government institutions were required to provide their strategic approach in line with their mandate that sought to support the achievement of the priorities articulated in the NDP.

For this period, the Government had adopted 14 outcome priorities based on the NDP. A minister was assigned to coordinate and account for the achievement of each outcome. The President signed performance agreements with all ministers that set out their respective deliverables. This was in addition to the established practice of entering into performance agreements with directors-general and other senior managers in the Public Service. In order to achieve these, the NDP and its proposals were to be implemented in the following phases:

• **Unlocking implementation - 2013**

- Implementing programmes that did not require additional resources and long lead times.
- Identifying critical first steps to unlock implementation.
- Preparing the 2014-19 MTSF as the first five-year building block of the NDP.
- Focusing on areas where implementation of existing policies needed to improve.
- Conducting focused dialogues to overcome obstacles to implementation.

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- **2014-2019 planning cycle.** The 2014-2019 planning cycle had to be viewed as the first in a series of five-year planning cycles that would advance the goals of the NDP. The equivalent planning cycle at local government level would be equally important.
- **2019-2024 and 2024-2029 planning cycles.** This phase of the NDP will be used to initiate the remaining activities. It will build on previous cycles and be informed by the review of performance.

1.2 Objectives of the Report

The NDP follows a holistic approach towards achieving its main goals, which cut across various departments. However, the focus of this paper is limited to the role played by the former Departments of Rural Development and Land Reform (DRDLR) and Agriculture Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF), as they were required to work together in terms of Chapter 6 of the NDP, titled “inclusive rural economy”. Chapter 6 envisions rural areas that are spatially, socially and economically well integrated, where residents have economic growth, food security and jobs, as well as improved access to basic services, healthcare and public transport. It envisages that by 2030 agriculture will create close to one million new jobs, contributing significantly to reducing overall unemployment.

As mentioned above, the NDP vision is to be implemented in three phases over a five-year planning cycle, which covers 2014-2019, 2019-2024 and 2024 -2029. The 2014-2019 MTSF is structured around 14 priority outcomes, which cover focus areas identified in the NDP. The DRDLR, supported by DAFF, is specifically required to lead in the implementation of Outcome 7: “Vibrant, equitable, sustainable rural communities contributing towards food security”. Both departments also contribute to Outcome 4: “Decent employment through inclusive growth” and Outcome 10: “Protect and enhance our environmental assets and natural resources”.

Since the first five-year cycle for the implementation of the NDP ended by the end of March 2019, it presents a perfect opportunity to review progress made to meet the stated objectives goals of the NDP in order to inform any interventions or changes needed to improve implementation for the remaining two cycles. This paper reviews progress in the implementation of the NDP over the five-year cycle (2014-2019 MTSF), particularly the implementation of outcomes 4, 7 and 10, within the context of the DRDLR and DAFF. It also identifies gaps and suggests measures that could be taken to ensure that the new Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development and the Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries meet their NDP targets relating to Chapter 6.

Accordingly, the purpose of the report is to:

- Report on progress made with the implementation of the NDP through the MTSF 2014-2019, in particular progress towards achieving radical economic transformation and inclusive growth, with special focus on chapter 6.
- Reflect on the performance of the former Departments of Rural Development and Land Reform and Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries towards implementation of the NDP.
- Suggest any interventions required to address challenges or gaps identified to ensure that the now consolidated Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development (DALRRD) and Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries meet the NDP targets for the remaining two five-year cycles with regard to chapter 6.

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Progress for each sector is presented in tabular format. Progress highlighted in red indicates targets that were not achieved, orange indicates lack of verifiable evidence or outcomes have worsened, while those highlighted in green were either achieved or exceeded.

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2.1 Introduction

Chapter 6 of the NDP, titled “Inclusive Rural Economy”, envisions rural areas that are spatially, socially and economically well integrated, where residents have economic growth, food security and jobs, as well as improved access to basic services, healthcare, quality education and public transport. The NDP envisages that by 2030 agriculture will create close to one million new jobs, contributing significantly to reducing overall unemployment. The NDP acknowledges that the economic growth of the agricultural sector has been constrained by insufficient progress in increasing production efficiency and accessing new markets and opportunities, the effect of globalisation on South Africa’s competitiveness and policy uncertainty, resulting in job losses. The NDP identifies six policy imperatives, which were incorporated into the 2014-19 MTSF. The following are critical to the agricultural sector:

- Improved food security;
- Smallholder farmer development and support (technical, financial, infrastructure) for agrarian transformation; and
- Growth of sustainable rural enterprises and industries characterised by strong rural-urban linkages, increased investment in agro-processing, trade development and access to markets and financial services—resulting in rural job creation.

Further, the NDP acknowledges that the Agricultural sector has potential to create approximately one million jobs by 2030. In order to achieve this, South Africa needs to:

- Expand irrigated agriculture;
- Convert some under-used land in communal areas and transform land reform projects into commercial production;
- Support agricultural sectors and regions that show potential;
- Support job creation in the downstream and upstream industries;
- Find creative combinations between opportunities, such as prioritising successful farmers in communal areas; and
- Develop strategies that give new entrants access to product value-chain and support from better-resourced players.

The expansion of small-scale production in agriculture, forestry and fisheries is essential to creating a dynamic rural economy and inclusivity in former homeland areas. Given appropriate infrastructure and marketing support, primary production can provide a meaningful livelihood to many more people than it presently does, while underpinning household-level and local food security through more robust local food networks. The continued pressure on agriculture to increase output per unit of land poses an additional challenge of ensuring that the natural resource base is protected. A major limitation in increasing output in agriculture, especially smallholder producers, has been uncoordinated support across Government. Support in this context entails extension services, training, financial support, market information and related forms of support to smallholder producers.

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2.2 Overview of NDP for the Agricultural Sector

In translating the broad policy imperatives of the NDP, the Vision was supported by outcome 4 (decent employment through inclusive economic growth) and outcome 7 (comprehensive rural development and land reform) of Government's 2014-2019 MTSF. Further to the outcomes, MTSF sub-outcomes and component indicators were developed and assigned to the respective sector departments for implementation. Over the 2014-2019 period, the former Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF) focused on improving food security and safety; creating jobs; increasing the contribution of the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sectors to Gross Domestic Product (GDP); and upgrading infrastructure. This section includes a more detailed focus on the implementation of outcomes 4 and 7 by the former Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries.³

i. Outcome 4: Decent employment through inclusive economic growth

The MTSF aimed to drive inclusive growth. This requires that economic agencies increase their capacity in terms of institutional structure and skills to promptly address blockages to investment and job creation in their areas of responsibility, as well as to identify and facilitate sustainable programmes that can act as catalysts for long-term economic development. Agricultural employment is critical for improving incomes and inclusion of rural people. The relevant departments, provinces and municipalities were meant to work together to improve district-based planning as the basis for a holistic approach to achieving the targets for new smallholders and commercial agricultural employment set in the New Growth Path. The former Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries was meant to prioritise the expansion of technologies to support increasing levels of development among smallholders in agriculture and agro-processing as a driver of employment and economic growth in rural areas. The plan was to build on the systematic push under the National Infrastructure Plan (NIP) to overcome the backlogs in infrastructure left in the former "homeland" regions. This sub-outcome supplements Outcome 7 by focusing on employment creation in particular through smallholders, which is the core concern for inclusive growth in this regard.

³ This section of the paper will focus on the agriculture sector.

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Table 1: Sub Outcome 1: Productive investment is effectively crowded in through the infrastructure build programme

Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Infrastructure will support productive investment and growth	New productive investments utilise the infrastructure provided by every Strategic Infrastructure Programme (SIP) ⁴	New Indicator	2019: Every major economic infrastructure project will have a list of productive investment projects utilising its key elements by 2019	SIP 11 Progress Report for the MTSF period has not been compiled. The National Agricultural Marketing Council (NAMC) compiled the agro-logistics infrastructure database in 2013. However, there is no indication of finalised investments made in the sector.
Ensure monitoring of off-takes by end users on the infrastructure programme	Measurable improvement in support of end-users	New Indicator	2019: List of off-take agreements for major economic infrastructure where applicable	

Source: The Presidency (2014) g

Table 2: Sub Outcome 2: The productive sectors account for a growing share of production and employment

Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Agricultural Policy Action Plan (APAP) developed, implemented and reviewed regularly in terms of impact on growth, employment, rural incomes, investment, output, exports and African regional development	APAP sector and cross-cutting interventions towards growth, employment creation, higher rural incomes and strong exports underway	New Indicator	2019: All APAP sector and cross-cutting interventions being implemented	The APAP was developed as an apex policy document to guide the sector in identifying key industries that have high potential for growth. The Department has not produced a consolidated report on APAP activities for the MTSF period.

⁴ This was to be coordinated by the Presidential Infrastructure Coordinating Commission, supported by Economic Development, Trade and Industry, Mineral Resources, Agriculture Forestry and Fisheries, Rural Development and Land Reform, Transport.

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Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Implementation of the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP)	CAADP Compact and investment plans underway	New Indicator	<p>2019: 95% of CAADP investment plans implemented</p> <p>10% investment in agriculture and rural development (as a share of the GDP)</p> <p>6% economic growth</p>	<p>South Africa ratified the 2003 Maputo Declaration, and also re-committed to the CAADP process in the 2014 Malabo Declaration.</p> <p>The country has not managed to develop implementable (financially viable & backed) investment plans.</p> <p>The main impediment seems to be lack of institutionalisation of CAADP.</p>
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries Market and Trade Development Strategy	Trade and Development Strategy and cross-cutting interventions towards growth, employment creation and higher rural incomes underway	New Indicator	2019: 95% of Agricultural, Forestry and Fisheries Market and Trade Development Strategy implemented	<p>The Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries Market and Trade Development Strategy was not developed. However, under Programme 4: Trade Promotion and Market Access, the Department implements the promotion of economic development, trade and market access for agriculture, forestry and fisheries products; and foster international relations for the sector. It is under this programme that the Department participates in trade negotiations,</p>

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				implements its International Relations Strategy and concludes trade agreements.
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Source: The Presidency (2014) g

Table 3: Sub Outcome 5: Spatial imbalances in economic opportunities are addressed through expanded employment in agriculture, the build programme and densification in the metros

Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Development of smallholder production in context of improved district planning and link to land reform, extension, marketing and other systems	Plan to support smallholders developed and incorporated in APAP, with clear annual targets	New Indicator	2019: 300 000 new smallholders (producing for market) by 2019	<p>The Department reports on this indicator under Programme 3 through the provincial departments of agriculture.</p> <p>The programme has dismally failed, as the Department has not been able to meet its annual targets over the MTSF (building up to 300 000). The scenario is worsened when considering the number of smallholder farmers that are producing for market.</p> <p>Lastly, there has been a myriad of challenges regarding the reliability, appropriateness, and verification of</p>

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				information when the reported performance was audited by the Auditor General of South Africa.
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Source: The Presidency (2014) g

Table 4: Sub Outcome 8: Economic opportunities for historically excluded and vulnerable groups are expanded and the number of sustainable small business and cooperatives is improved markedly

Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Programmes to ensure increased access to employment and entrepreneurship for black women and youth in the context of stronger support for emerging and smaller enterprises overall	Youth in employment or Education Share of women in formal employment		2019: Measurable increase	The Department has implemented various awareness programmes and events that focus on women and youth. It should, however, be noted that these were not necessarily institutionalised nor systematic in a manner that they resulted in a measurable increase.
Provide coaching, incubation, intensive support and financing to sustain existing small businesses and cooperatives, as well as to expand the sector	Strategy and programmes to support existing, as well as develop new small business and cooperatives, to facilitate access to formal markets. Percentage growth in the number registered small		2019: Development of systems to determine sustainability. Annual incremental shift towards 30% target by 2019, above current baseline	The Department has annual targets on the number of cooperatives that are supported, as well the number of farmers that are SA-GAP certified that has varied over the MTSF under Programme 4: Trade Promotion and Market Access. The Department has consistently met its targets in this regard. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Given the fact that the Department has not established a data baseline on the number of cooperatives that require support or the number of farmers that require SA-GAP certification or even other types of certification (export, abattoir etc.), it is not

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	business and cooperatives. Percentage of new small business and cooperatives that are supported and that are still operating one year after support provided.			possible to determine the impact of the support provided over the 5-year period. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lastly, though the Department has had various funding instruments, such as AgriBee and Mafisa, these have had lacklustre performance, as they were managed or disbursed through third party arrangements.
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Source: The Presidency (2014) g

Table 5: Sub Outcome 10: Investment in research, development and innovation supports inclusive growth by enhancing productivity of existing and emerging enterprises and improving the living conditions of the poor

Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Emerging/new industries strategies aligned with IPAP and regularly monitored in terms of long-run growth and competitiveness, job creation and export potential	Emerging/new industry sector and cross-cutting interventions towards growth, employment creation and higher incomes for poor households underway		2019: All emerging/new industry sector and cross-cutting interventions being implemented	The APAP was developed as an apex policy document to guide the sector in identifying key industries that have high potential for growth. The Department has not produced a consolidated report on APAP activities for the MTSF period.

Source: The Presidency (2014) g

ii. Outcome 7: Comprehensive rural development and land reform

Under Outcome 7, titled *Comprehensive Rural Development and Land Reform*, there are three sub-outcomes that the former Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries was

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mandated to implement as part of the 2014-2019 MTSF. In terms of Sub-outcome 1: *Improved Land Administration and Spatial Planning for Integrated Development* in rural areas, the loss of agricultural land use was deemed of paramount importance and required urgent attention. In terms of Sub-outcome 3: *Improved Food Security*, the NDP highlighted that food insecurity still remains a challenge for the country, especially at rural household level, notwithstanding the development of the Integrated Food Security Strategy (IFSS, 2002) to streamline, harmonise and integrate the diverse food security programmes. Part of the identified challenge was that food security is also threatened by the under-utilisation of productive agricultural resources in communal lands and land reform projects. In this regard, the NDP made reference to a number of interventions to be implemented to improve food security. These included the expanded use of irrigation, security of land tenure, especially for women, and the promotion of social protection, including nutrition education.

In terms of Sub-outcome 4: *Smallholder Producers' Development and Support* (technical, financial, infrastructure) for agrarian transformation, the NDP underpinned the fact that the economic growth of the agricultural sector has been constrained by declining numbers of commercial producers, whilst seeing a simultaneous increase in the size of farming units and a resultant decline in employment. Between 1950 and the present, the number of commercial farming units in primary agriculture has declined from almost 120 000 to approximately 38 000.⁵ The sector has ineffectively grown to the exclusion of smallholder farmers, and smaller commercial enterprises across the value chain. Growing the sector (commercial and smallholder producers) is a key issue highlighted in the Industrial Development Plan and the Agricultural Policy Action Plan (APAP). The below tables outline the various actions, indicators, baselines, and targets as per the respective sub-outcomes.

Table 6: Sub-outcome 1: Improved land administration and spatial planning for integrated development in rural areas

Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Institutionalise the regulatory framework for land use to guide and support development initiatives	Cabinet approval of Preservation and Development of Agricultural Land Framework Act (PDALFA)	New indicator	Implementation management of Preservation and Development of Agricultural Land Framework Act (PDALFA)	The Bill is still under development, and has not been submitted to Cabinet. It is most likely a long way from being tabled in Parliament.

⁵ DPME (2014)

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<p>Strengthen coordination across the three spheres of government and external stakeholders to implement the Comprehensive Rural Development Programme (CRDP) in line with the spatial development plans</p>	<p>Intergovernmental Relations and Stakeholder Management Strategy developed and finalised</p>	<p>New indicator</p>	<p>Intergovernmental Relations and Stakeholder Management Strategy approved by March 2015</p>	<p>The Department reported in 2018/19 that the Intergovernmental Relations and Stakeholder Management Strategy was developed.</p>
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Source: The Presidency (2014) h

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Table 7: Sub-outcome 3: Improved food security

Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Implement the comprehensive food security and nutrition strategy	Number of people benefiting from food security and nutrition initiatives 65.8 per cent of households	Food Security and nutrition policy and Strategy 146 000 producers supported.	4,31 million vulnerable people benefiting from food security and nutrition initiatives, translating into 1,6 million households by March 2019	<p><u>The Department leads and coordinates the national food security initiatives across the public sector</u> and was meant to be in a position to collate an annual report on food security interventions. This work was done under Programme 3: Food Security and Agrarian Reform.</p> <p>However, though the Department has reported that these reports have been compiled, there is no indication on what has been achieved and the improvements gained in so far as food and nutrition security.</p>
Develop under-utilised land in communal areas and land reform projects for production	Number of hectares of under-utilised land in communal areas cultivated for production	To be determined: under-utilised land in communal areas Land reform projects: 4 m ha (4860 farms)	1 million hectares by March 2019	<p>The Department launched Fetsa Tlala⁶ with the objective of attaining this sub-outcome.</p> <p>Due to the implementation model and lack of additional allocations for this programme, the Department has since abandoned this initiative, as it deems it to be an unfunded mandate.</p>

Source: The Presidency (2014) h

⁶ Government's flagship food security programme.

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Table 8: Sub-outcome 4: Smallholder producers' development and support (technical, financial, infrastructure) for agrarian transformation

Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Develop and implement policies promoting the development and support of smallholder producers	Policies promoting the development and support to smallholder producers in place and implemented	Food Security and nutrition policy and strategy Draft Agricultural Action Plan Policy	Smallholder producers policies implemented by March 2019	<p>The Department has started an Operation Phakisa process that sought to develop the Draft National Policy on Comprehensive Producer Development Support in the 2018/19 financial year.</p> <p>The draft policy sought to be the overall national policy for the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector in South Africa that will regulate and guide interventions (support services) provided to the various categories of producers by Government.</p>
Expand land under irrigation	Number of hectares under irrigation used by Smallholder producers	To be determined	An additional 1250 hectares under irrigation by March 2019	The Department has reneged on this proposal and argues that there is scientific evidence that argues that it is not feasible to expand irrigation in South Africa, regardless of the evidence provided by the sector input in the development of the NDP.

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Actions	Indicator	Baseline	Targets	Progress by March 2019
Provide support to smallholder producers in order to ensure production efficiencies	Number of smallholder producers receiving support	To be determined	An additional 80 000 smallholder producers by March 2019	<p>The Department reports on this indicator under Programme 3 through the provincial departments of agriculture.</p> <p>The programme has dismally failed, as the Department has not been able to meet its annual targets over the MTEF (building up to 80 000).</p> <p>Lastly, there has been a myriad of challenges regarding the reliability, appropriateness, and verification of information when the reported performance was audited by the Auditor General of South Africa</p>

Source: The Presidency (2014)

2.3 Progress on the Implementation of the NDP

The NDP was intended to rally the nation around a high growth strategy. Instead of a growth rate of 5.4%, the average growth rate between 2012 and 2019, the GDP growth rate was estimated at 1.4%. Consequently, the economy will be much less advanced in 2030 than the NDP projection. It is considered a given that the NDP's successful implementation depended heavily on the capacity of the State to translate its goals into "implementable programmes and projects along the different tiers of government – provinces, municipalities and local government – culminating in achieving the set goals and objectives within the designated timeframes".⁷ This includes questioning the quality and capacity of people at the

⁷ The Presidency (2019)

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three levels of government to align the NDP with their plans. There are three key public policy areas that have proven challenging for the South African Government: “the ability to implement policy; enforce legislation; and deliver services”.⁸

The NDP set a target for the creation of 643 000 direct jobs and 326 000 indirect jobs in the agriculture and agro-processing sectors by 2030. The main criticisms of the NDP proposals were that it focused on export-led growth in the agricultural sector to increase output. However, studies of economic growth in rural economies have illustrated that export-led growth is less effective than an increase in production and livestock, particularly in Africa. Further criticisms include that the NDP does not consider agriculture within the context of food security. South Africa generally enjoys food security, but due to consumption of more than one staple food, it has started to become reliant on food imports. Agriculture also has the potential to positively contribute to the country's nutrition and this, given the high levels of poverty in South Africa, can have a multiplier effect in contributing to reducing the levels of poverty and inequality. South Africa has a total surface area of 122 million hectares, 17 million hectares (14%) of which is arable.⁹ Of the arable land, only 1.3 million hectares are under irrigation, with rainfall being erratic and unevenly distributed. Agriculture is a sector which is heavily influenced by weather patterns, as well as being exposed to changes in the global markets.

Though the agricultural sector in South Africa's remains one of the most productive on the African Continent, it is currently under strain because of high input costs, political uncertainty, global price volatility, climate change and stressed farmers. South Africa has untapped potential in the form of land, labour and natural resources. The number of jobs created per unit of investment in agriculture is higher than in other sectors. However, since the 2016/17 drought, the agricultural sector has shrunk in its contribution to the GDP and shed jobs despite the fact that the NDP sets it at the forefront of job creation. It is an accepted fact in development economics that agriculture usually shrinks as economies develop (through structural transformation). In South Africa, however, there is still potential for job growth. Economic participation in rural areas is low and the percentage of rural employment in agriculture is very low by global standards. Rural employment could grow with reformed land tenure, support to farmers, expanded social services, higher agricultural output, mining social investment and tourism.

Lastly, the NDP needed to be aligned to the country's budgetary commitments, or else it will not live up to all its promises. For the NDP proposals to materialise, the country's priority-setting needed to focus succinctly on drivers of economic development in order to pursue the goal of inclusive economic growth. What could arguably be the real challenge in implementing the NDP proposals is the disjuncture between Government policy and economic policy. The NDP was deemed to be an overarching policy directive that should have guided the various sectoral plans. Embedded in this assertion was the critical assumption underlying the Chapter 6 scenarios that the State can develop the capacities required to implement land and agrarian reform, and to engage in effective co-ordination and policy alignment across these and related sectors. It seems, however, that the assumptions underlying the agricultural sector's initiatives deviated fundamentally from those of the NDP.

⁸ Ibid

⁹ DAFF (2014)

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2.4 Recommendations

Given the fact that the NDP was meant to serve as an overarching blueprint that should guide the strategic interventions and programmes in the sector; the following key considerations must be made by all the relevant stakeholders (both private & public):

- Invest in Research and Development (R&D) that promotes increased productivity and production.
- Develop an efficient marketing system that lowers the cost of agro-logistics for rural farmers.
- Address climate induced change adverse production conditions and build climate resilient production systems and a locally integrated food economy.
- Adopt technological solutions that drive smart agricultural technological innovations for efficient resource allocations (e.g. precision irrigation, satellite monitoring of plants pests etc.).
- Reduce post-harvest losses through improved on-farm processing and warehousing solutions.
- Create incentives for energy efficiency and green energy harvesting for on-farm use (low carbon footprint).
- Encourage expansion in labour-intensive agricultural commodities, as identified in the NDP: fruit, nuts and vegetables, as well as less labour-intensive commodities with potential for growth, such as livestock products.
- Develop tailor-made support packages for targeted market-oriented smallholder farmers in an expanded land reform programme to create large numbers of new employment opportunities.
- Deter anti-competitive behaviour throughout the various agro-food value chains in order to create a more level playing field, particularly for new entrants.

2.5 Conclusion

South Africa's rural strategy aims to strengthen food security and agricultural competitiveness, while lifting marginalised rural households, especially in former homeland areas, out of poverty. Chronic underdevelopment with its social, economic and cultural dimensions still continues in many rural areas. To transform the rural economy, investment is required in infrastructure, services, skills and productivity. By 2030, the rural economy (agriculture) was intended to create close to one million new jobs, contributing significantly to reducing overall unemployment. The agricultural sector has undergone major structural changes that were mainly driven by drought, under-investment, plant and animal pests and diseases, stringent sanitary and phyto-sanitary protocols from trade partners, as well other macro-economic factors that constrained growth and development of the sector.

Though progress has been made towards realising the goals of the NDP 2030 across the economic, social and governance sectors, progress is uneven. Furthermore, performance on NDP 2030 actions, which require cooperation across multiple departments, spheres of government or non-governmental stakeholders, shows poor implementation progress. The slow/poor implementation of the NDP could be ascribed to the fact that there are too many Government priorities that are accorded equal weighting and status. As a result, resources are thinly spread, given the current economic environment. Inadequate information systems in Government to track progress towards the NDP 2030 is also identified as a key challenge.

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3.1 Introduction

The NDP states that since 1994 the main challenge for rural development has been marginalisation of the poor, with many rural areas and households trapped in a vicious cycle of poverty. Thus, the main objectives of the NDP is to focus Government's efforts in addressing the core challenges of poverty, unemployment and inequality facing the South African society, which is more evident in rural areas. In this regard, the NDP prioritises job creation, poverty reduction, the reduction of inequality and growing an inclusive economy by 2030.

The purpose of this section is to review progress made in the implementation of the NDP over the 2014-2019 MTSF, particularly the implementation of outcome 7 within the scope of the former Department of Rural Development and Land Reform (DRDLR). It also identifies gaps and suggests measures for Parliament to strengthen its oversight and for the Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development (DALRRD) to ensure that the NDP targets with regard to the rural development and land reform sector are met.

3.2 Overview of the NDP for Rural Development and Land Reform sector¹⁰

The vision of the NDP with regard to rural development is set out in Chapter 6, which calls for an integrated and inclusive rural economy as follows:

By 2030, South Africa's remote areas should have greater participation in the economic, social and political landscape of the country, with access to quality basic services. The vision will include better integration and this can be achieved through land reform and poverty alleviation, with expansion in irrigated agriculture being the driving force. The support of human capital will be achieved through the use of basic services in health, quality education and social security. Access to basic social and infrastructural services is a high priority for many rural households.

Chapter 6 of the NDP provides for a differentiated rural development strategy that focuses on:

- Agricultural development, based on successful land reform, employment creation and strong environmental safeguards. To achieve this, irrigated agriculture and dry-land production should be expanded, with emphasis on smallholder farmers, where possible. To this end, established agricultural industries must be enabling partners.
- Quality basic services, particularly education, health care and public transport. Well-functioning and supported communities enable people to seek economic opportunities. This allows them to develop their communities further through remittances and the transfer of skills, which will contribute to the local economy.
- In areas with greater economic potential, industries such as agro-processing, tourism, fisheries (in coastal areas) and small enterprise development should be developed with market support. Special focus to be placed on enhancing skills and capabilities of rural women entrepreneurs with access to land and finance.

¹⁰ Information below is sourced from the Presidency (2010).

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Key proposals for the rural development and land reform sector contained in the NDP are:

- **(i) Expand agriculture and create an additional 1 million jobs in the sector** - This policy directive would be realised by investing in water resource and irrigation infrastructure; investing in providing market linkages for small-scale farmers in the communal and land reform area; creating tenure for communal farmers; supporting Public-Private partnerships; and improving and extending skills development and training.
- **Land Reform** - Land reform can increase the potential for growth and employment in the agricultural sector. A land reform scheme should thus enable rapid transfer of agricultural land to black beneficiaries; ensure sustainable production on transferred land; establish institutional arrangements to monitor land markets against undue opportunism, corruption and speculation; bring land transfer targets in line with fiscal and economic realities; and offer white commercial farmers and organised industry bodies the opportunity to significantly contribute to the success of black farmers through mentorships.
- **Food Security** - Investigate measures to close the urban/rural food price gap.
- **Farm worker empowerment and labour Relations** - Commercial farms, prior to 1994, fell outside the parameters of labour legislation, leading to ultra-exploitation of farm workers.¹¹ While the standard of many South Africans has improved after 1994, the living and working conditions of farm workers have not improved. Many have been evicted or are faced with evictions. It is a known fact that farm workers and their families are among the poorest people in South Africa.¹²

MTSF 2014-2019

In order to achieve the vision as outlined in Chapter 6, the NDP identified six strategic policy imperatives (priorities) that were to be the focus of the 2014 – 2019 MTSF. Of particular relevance to the land reform and rural development sector is Outcome 7 of the MTSF, which is aimed at creating vibrant, equitable, sustainable rural communities contributing towards food security, as per table 9 below:

Table 9: Outcome 7: creating vibrant, equitable, sustainable rural communities contributing towards food security

Sub-Outcomes/ Priorities	Description	Targets	Progress by March 2019
7.1	Improved land administration (tenure reform) and spatial planning for integrated development in rural areas	National Rural Spatial Development Framework approved by March 2018	NSDF in the process of being submitted to Cabinet for approval. The Draft NSDF was published for public comment in January 2020

¹¹ Helliker (2013).

¹² Atkinson *et al* (2004).

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Sub-Outcomes/ Priorities	Description	Targets	Progress by March 2019
		Nine provinces supported to develop Spatial Development Frameworks (SDFs) by 2019	Nine Provinces supported
		234 (100%) Local Municipalities Implementing SPLUMA by March 2019	100%
7.2	Sustainable Land Reform contributing to agrarian transformation (restitution, redistribution, tenure reform and development).	Acquire 2million ha for Previously Disadvantaged Individuals	1 013 026 ha (50.6%)
		50% of acquired ha by March 2019 allocated to smallholder producers	535 766 ha (52% or 1 013 026 ha acquired)
		200 000 (10%) of hectares allocated to farm dwellers or labour tenants by March 2019	147 134 ha (14%) – target exceeded
7.3	Improved Food Security	4.3 million people vulnerable to hunger benefiting from food security and nutrition initiatives translating to 1.6 million households	6.7 million people benefiting, translating into 2.6 million households
		1 million ha of under-utilised land in communal areas cultivated for production	763 715 (76.3%)
7.4	Smallholder producers' development and support for agrarian transformation.	1 250 ha under irrigation used by smallholder producers.	23 480 ha
		300 000 smallholder farmers receiving support.	255 348 smallholder producers supported (85%)
		1 741 farms under RADP	1 171 farms under RADP (63%).
7.5	Increase access to quality infrastructure and functional, services, particularly education, health and	15.5 million households have access to safe and reliable drinking water	742 238 households access to piped water

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Sub-Outcomes/ Priorities	Description	Targets	Progress by March 2019
	public transport in rural areas.	2.2 million households have access to sanitation	1.3 million households access to sanitation service (57% of the target)
		1.1 million households have access to grid (electricity).	84 138 houses connected to grid.
7.6	Growth of sustainable rural enterprises and industries – resulting in rural job creation.	44 rural districts completed	44 rural districts' plans completed.
		615 existing rural enterprises and 18 existing industries supported	15 644 rural enterprises and 175 existing industries supported.
		924 140 rural people employed through rural development initiatives.	622 946 jobs created.
		90 000 skilled people	595 777 rural people trained in various skills development programmes

Source: DALRRD (2019a) and DPME (2019).

It is expected that through these strategic imperatives and recommendations, the DALRRD will contribute firstly towards the reduction of the rural unemployment rate and the number of households vulnerable to hunger; secondly ensure an increase in the percentage of ownership of productive land by previously disadvantaged individuals; and thirdly ensure sustainable production on transferred land. This constitutes the yard stick against which to measure its success towards implementation of the NDP. However, it is critical that coordination by relevant departments, led by the DALRRD across the three spheres of government and external stakeholders in the rural and agricultural sector, should be strengthened.

3.3 Progress on the Implementation of the NDP

In line with Government priorities as outlined in the NDP and the 2014-2019 MTSF, the Department prioritises poverty eradication and job creation, which affect rural areas. It introduced programmes such as the Comprehensive Rural Development Programme (CRDP) as the main tool for reduction of poverty and food insecurity in rural areas. In addition, the Rural Enterprise and Industrial Development (REID), Rural Infrastructure Development (RID) and National Rural Youth Service Corps (NARYSEC) are used as key programmes for job creation and skills development in rural areas.

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i. Sub-outcome 1: Improved Land Administration and Spatial Planning

Spatial Planning and Land Use Management Act

Before 1994, land use planning and settlement patterns in South Africa was governed and shaped by different governments aimed at supporting the segregated government system of the time. As a result, in 1994, South Africa inherited a complex, disjointed and racially-based spatial planning and land use management system, which has resulted in unequal and inefficient settlement patterns in urban and rural areas. It has also created tension between the three spheres of government and key national departments over who has responsibility for spatial and land use planning. In 1995, the Development Facilitation Act (DFA), 1995 was put in place to address challenges in spatial planning. However, parts of the DFA were found unconstitutional by the Constitutional Court in 2010. The Spatial Planning and Land Use Management Act (SPLUMA, Act No. 16 of 2013) was passed by Parliament in 2013 and came into operation on 1 July 2015 to replace the DFA. The main aim of SPLUMA is to address the fragmented and unsustainable spatial development patterns in the country. It therefore creates a single integrated legal system dealing with spatial planning in a uniform way for the country.¹³ The Act obliges all three spheres of government to prepare Spatial Development Frameworks (SDFs) and requires alignment and consistency between these frameworks.

The main target under this priority was the implementation of SPLUMA and the development of the National Spatial Development Framework (NSDF), which should have been done by March 2019. By the end of March, the NSDF was not approved as planned. Instead, a second draft was available, which was in the process of being submitted to Cabinet for approval. All nine provinces were supported to develop Spatial Development Frameworks as planned and municipalities were provided with technical support towards implementation of SPLUMA.¹⁴ However, the main challenge was that municipalities did not always prioritise the implementation of the Act. The situation was exacerbated by the lack of capacity to implement the Act across all three spheres of government. In addition, traditional leaders have been unwilling to participate in the programme, as they claim they were not properly consulted as custodians of tribal land.¹⁵

In general, a lot of work was done and structures created to improve land administration and spatial planning, in particular through the legislative framework such as SPLUMA. However, effective implementation of SPLUMA will require competence and determination, particularly at municipal level. It is appreciated that in line with the NDP the draft NSDF prepared in accordance with SPLUMA was published for public comment in January 2020 and hopefully it will be finalised and implemented in the 2020/21 financial year.

ii. Sub-outcome 2: Sustainable Land Reform contributing to Agrarian Transformation

Research shows that an intervention which transfers assets such as land to the poor has the potential to reduce the level of poverty and create jobs, especially in rural areas.¹⁶ It should be noted that employment resulting from land reform projects benefits both the workers and beneficiaries who manage the farms.¹⁷ It also enables some household

¹³ South African Cities Network (2015).

¹⁴ DRDLR (2019a).

¹⁵ DRDLR (2020).

¹⁶ May (2010); IFAD (2011).

¹⁷ DRDLR (2012a).

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members to get employment closer to their families and thus limits the number of people migrating from rural areas to urban areas in search of employment.¹⁸ Despite the significance of land access to poverty alleviation, land ownership in South Africa is highly skewed due to past discriminatory policies.

Since 1994, the South African Government embarked on a land reform programme based on three pillars, namely, restitution (settling claims of land lost under Apartheid through either restoration or financial compensation); redistribution (transferring of White-owned agricultural land to Black people) and tenure reform (aimed at providing more secure access to land in communal areas and commercial farms). Through these programmes, the Government set itself the target of delivering 30% of commercial agricultural land by 2014, which is 24.5 million hectares. However, this target, which has been extended since 1999, seems to have fallen away. In terms of the NDP, targets set relate to redistribution and land tenure for farm workers and farm dwellers.

Redistribution

The purpose of land redistribution is to address the legacy of racial inequality in accessing land and creating opportunities for development. It aims to provide Black people with access to land for residential and productive use to improve their livelihoods. Transferring of productive agricultural land to previously disadvantaged South Africans is important in reducing poverty and food insecurity in rural areas, and also contributes towards sustainable agrarian transformation, which are key outputs for Outcome 7.

There is general acceptance from civil society, landowners' and landless people's organisations that the pace of land reform is very slow, although they do not agree on the reasons therefore. Even Government has acknowledged the poor progress of land reform. The former Department of Performance Monitoring and Evaluation (DPME) reported that by the midterm (2014/15 – 2016/17), the Department had redistributed 10.6% (8.7 million hectares) of the targeted 30% (24.6m ha) of agricultural land for distribution to Previously Disadvantaged Individuals (PDIs) and only 40% of the 2019 target was distributed since 2014.¹⁹

The 2019 target was for the former DRDLR to transfer two million hectares of productive land ownership to PDIs from 2014/15 to 2018/19. By the end of 2018/19, the Department has transferred 1.013 million hectares, which is 50.6% of the 2019 target.²⁰ Of the 1.013 million hectares acquired by 2019, 52.9% (535 766 ha) was allocated to smallholder producers, which is more than the 50% target. However, it should be noted that the Department did not achieve the target of acquiring two million hectares by 2019, in which case it would have been required to transfer 1 million hectares to smallholder producers.

Land Tenure

The purpose of tenure reform is to strengthen the rights of people whose land tenure is insecure as a result of discriminatory laws and practices in the past. These include farm workers, labour tenants and rural households living on privately owned land, and people living in communal areas, largely in the former homelands.

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹The Presidency (2017).

²⁰ DRDLR (2019).

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The major achievement has been the passing of pieces of legislation to strengthen the rights of farm workers and farm dwellers, such as the Extension of Security of Tenure Act (ESTA, Act No. 62 of 1997) and the Labour Tenants Act (LTA, Act No. 3 of 1996). Both Acts mandate the relevant Minister to provide land ownership to farm dwellers and labour tenants as individuals. They can also claim their land through the Restitution of Land Rights Act (Act No. 22 of 1994). However, the Minister failed to use these Acts to buy land for farm dwellers and labour tenants.

In terms of the MTSF, the Department was to transfer 10% of the land acquired for PDIs to farm workers and farm dwellers by 2019. Of the 1.013 million hectares acquired by 2019, 14.5% (147 134 ha) was allocated to farm workers or dwellers, which means the target was exceeded by 4%. However, it should be noted that the 1.013 million hectares acquired was below the 2 million hectares to be acquired by 2019. In terms of structures created, the major achievement has been having functioning District Land Committees and Land Rights Management Committees (LRMC). However, it is not clear what measure is used to determine the functionality of these structures.

iii. Sub-outcome 3: Improved Food Security

The right to food in South is entrenched in the following provisions contained in the Bill of Rights in Chapter 2 of the Constitution²¹: section 27(1)(b);²² section 28(1)(c)²³ and section 35(2)(e).²⁴ In terms of food security, the 2018 General Household Survey shows that 20.2% of South African households had inadequate or severely inadequate access to food.

The Comprehensive Rural Development Programme (CRDP)

A key feature of the work of the former DRDLR towards achieving Outcome 7 has been the conceptualisation and launch of the Comprehensive Rural Development Programme (CRDP). Through the CRDP, Government seeks to eliminate poverty and food insecurity in rural areas by maximising the use and management of natural resources.

The Department, through the CRDP, has initiated the establishment of household, institutional (in schools and health centres) and community gardens in rural wards. It also provided households with seeds and fenced community gardens to reduce theft and destruction by animals. Jojo tanks (rainwater harvesting containers) were provided for households to utilise rainwater for food gardens. Food gardens have been created as measures to support rural communities to grow their own food and thus protect the poor from rising food prices for the purpose of reducing food insecurity. The key finding from studies conducted was that household and community food gardens have improved livelihoods of beneficiaries where they were implemented appropriately.²⁵

Although the percentage of households and the number of people vulnerable to hunger has decreased between 2011 and 2018²⁶, the decline has been driven by widespread access to social grants provided by the Department of Social Development rather than initiatives by

²¹ Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996.

²² Guarantees for everyone the right of access to sufficient food and water.

²³ Guarantees for every child the right to basic nutrition, shelter, basic health care and social services.

²⁴ Guarantees, amongst others, the right to adequate nutrition for detained persons.

²⁵ DRDLR & Presidency (2013).

²⁶ Stats SA (2019).

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the Department.²⁷ Notwithstanding that, there is substantial improvement in access to diverse and affordable food in rural areas.²⁸ However, despite the decline in vulnerability to hunger, a significant percentage of households (21%) continue to experience difficulty to access food.²⁹ Of those with inadequate access to food, 25.5% comprise rural households.³⁰ Also, research by the Financial and Fiscal Commission (FFC) found that most land reform beneficiaries tended to be worse off than those who did not benefit from land reform, particularly in respect of food security and household income.³¹

One Household One Hectare

The “One Household, One Hectare” (1H1HA) programme was launched in October 2015 in the Eastern Cape. Since then, it is implemented in all provinces. The main purpose of the Programme is to promote food security and improve rural livelihoods through allocating land to selected beneficiaries for subsistence farming, while the bigger plan is to transform the rural economy. The plan is to allocate one-hectare of land to every needy household in and outside of communal areas. Households are to be supported through the provision of equipment, production inputs and infrastructure in order to produce for consumption needs and to sell surplus, which are organised into primary cooperatives linked to the Agri-parks initiative.³²

In conclusion, the target for 2019 under this priority was to support 4.3 million people vulnerable to hunger, which translates into 1.6 million households supported by 2019. The Department exceeded this target, as it was able to support 6.7 million people that were vulnerable to hunger, which translates into 2.6 million households.³³ However, the target on the number of hectares of under-utilised land in communal areas cultivated for production was not achieved, as 763 715 hectares were cultivated instead of the one million hectares planned for, which translates into an achievement of only 76.3%.³⁴

iv. Sub-outcome 4: Smallholder Producers’ Development and Support for Agrarian Transformation

Recapitalisation and Development Programme

In line with the NDP and Outcome 7 of the 2014-2019 MTSF, the Department has indicated its ongoing commitment towards building sustainable rural livelihoods, partly through the Reconstruction and Development Programme (RADP, better known as Recap). The RADP was launched in 2008/9. It is responsible for making redistributed land productive and profitable through mechanised irrigation, farmer interventions and other interventions to improve farms. Through the programme, farmers are assisted with factors such as production inputs, infrastructure and machinery. However, one of the findings from the

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ DRDLR & Presidency: DPME (2013).

²⁹ Statistics South Africa (2011).

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ FFC (2016).

³² Nkwinti ((2017).

³³ DALRRD (2019).

³⁴ Ibid.

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evaluation of RADP is that the effectiveness of capacitating farmers/beneficiaries is not satisfactory.³⁵

The Department did not achieve most of its targets for 2019 under this priority. For instance, it did not achieve the target to ensure that 1 million hectares (50%) of the 2 million hectares of under-utilised land in communal areas is cultivated for production by 2019, as only 763 715 hectares were utilised, which translates into 76.3% target achievement.³⁶ The target on the number of farms under the RADP was also not achieved, as 1 171 farms were supported instead of the targeted 1 741 farms, which means only 63% of the target was reached. The target on the number of smallholder producers receiving support was also not achieved, as 255 348 smallholder producers were supported instead of the targeted 300 000, which represents 85% achievement.³⁷

Agri-Parks

Agri-parks have been established in all 44 district municipalities. The aim is to transform the rural economy by promoting the growth of the smallholder sector, creating employment opportunities and infrastructure development. The Agri-Parks framework clusters agricultural enterprises, and provides integrated value chain services and support, including farm infrastructure (including irrigation), extension services, production inputs (livestock, seedlings, fertilizer) and mechanisation inputs. In line with the NDP, the Agri-Parks initiative is expected to contribute to Government's targets of creating one million new jobs in rural economies by 2030, the development of 300 000 new small-scale farmers and the creation of 145 000 agro-processing jobs by 2019. By the end of 2018, through Agri-parks, about 5000 jobs had been created mainly in construction and agricultural production; 684 skills development opportunities were created, and 5000 hectares of land were under production.³⁸

v. Sub-outcome 5: Increased Access to Quality Infrastructure and Functional Services, particularly in Education, Healthcare and Public Transport

Comprehensive Rural Development Programme

Through the implementation of the CRDP, using the Rural Infrastructure Development (RID) component, infrastructure for basic services has been provided in rural areas. This includes infrastructure for electricity, water and sanitation, as well as building of clinics, houses, roads, community halls, multipurpose centres (presently known as Thusong Service Centres), etc. However, despite substantial investment in addressing backlogs in water, sanitation and electricity service delivery in rural areas, the delivery of these services continue to lag behind national norms. A major challenge is that where services are available, they are often of lower quality and more poorly maintained than in the rest of the country. Another challenge is providing sustainable basic services to a dispersed population at reasonable cost, which partly explains why most of the targets under this priority were not achieved. This means that much still needs to be done in clearing the backlogs in key services, such as water, sanitation, electricity, roads, education and health, which are significantly worse in rural areas than urban areas.³⁹ In addition, poor capacity in terms of

³⁵ The Presidency (2013a).

³⁶ DALRRD (2019).

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ DRDLR (2018)

³⁹ Ibid.

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staff and resources within local municipalities, which is more prominent in rural municipalities,⁴⁰ means that they are unable to invest effectively and maintain rural infrastructure, which impact on their capacity to create job opportunities.

vi. Sub-outcome 6: Growth of Sustainable Rural Enterprises and Industries resulting in rural job creation

As stated in the NDP, since 1994 the main challenge for rural development has been marginalisation of the poor, with many rural areas and households trapped in a vicious cycle of poverty. The unemployment rate is very high in rural areas, particularly in the former homelands.⁴¹ The situation is exacerbated by poor access to basic social and infrastructural services for many rural households, which further inhibits both formal and informal employment opportunities. Lack of economic opportunities in rural areas has increased rural-to-urban migration. This has further resulted in the overloading of urban infrastructure and unhygienic conditions in the informal human settlements, both within and around urban areas.

In most developing countries, agriculture and agriculture-related activities provide most of the employment in rural areas.⁴² Despite the agricultural sector's major potential for providing employment opportunities, its contribution to employment in South Africa has been on the decline. The 2016 Agricultural Household Survey indicates that 2.3 million households were engaged in agriculture compared to 2.9 million in 2011. The decrease of 19.1 per cent was mainly due to drought.⁴³ However, agriculture, especially small-scale farming, is still seen as a major contributor to job creation in the country. For example, in terms of the NDP, agriculture has the potential to create nearly one million jobs by 2030. Research also shows that an intervention that transfers assets, such as land, to the poor, has the potential to reduce the level of poverty and create jobs, especially in rural areas.⁴⁴ However, considering the current decline in agricultural production impacting on job creation, it might be impossible to meet the target of creating one million jobs by 2030.

CRDP

In cases where contractors have employed local people through CRDP, NARYSEC and EPWP projects, short-term jobs have been created. Development of rural enterprises, industries and cooperatives were initiated through the *Rural Enterprise and Industrial Development (REID)* programme. Almost all the targets relating to the development and support of rural enterprises, industries and cooperatives were achieved, with the exception of having a national rural incentive scheme in place and no information on the number of people employed in rural enterprises. For example, a total of 15 644 rural enterprises were established by 2019 against the target of 615 and 175 were supported against the target of 18.⁴⁵ In addition, 622 946 job opportunities and 595 777 skill development opportunities were created through RID and REID from 2014/15 to 2018/19.⁴⁶

⁴⁰ DPME (2012a).

⁴¹ Department of Performance, Monitoring and Evaluation (DPME) (2012a).

⁴² Machete (2004).

⁴³ The Presidency (2019)

⁴⁴ May (2010); IFAD (2011).

⁴⁵ DALRRD (2019a).

⁴⁶ DRDLR (2019b).

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National Rural Youth Service Corps

The National Rural Youth Service Corps (NARYSEC) was launched in September 2010 and has been rolled out in all provinces. It is a two-year skills development programme where young people from the age of 18-35 years from rural wards are trained in various skills while receiving a stipend for the duration of the programme. This is aimed at increasing the number of rural people employed and improving household income. However, claims have emerged that some of the beneficiaries are paid for in-service training while they are doing nothing or are not getting any valuable skills.⁴⁷ It became clear during Committee deliberations on NARYSEC that there is no proper supervision of the programme by the DRDLR, as it could not provide details of what the beneficiaries are actually doing and whether the programme has increased their chances of entering the labour market after the training.

Although a large number of young people have been recruited, the challenge is that there is no comprehensive exit strategy in place to ensure that recruits can use skills attained to be self-employed or, alternatively, to be placed with existing enterprises. It was a major challenge to persuade employers to take youth in for job experience.⁴⁸

Expanded Public Works Programme

The Expanded Public Works Programme (EPWP) was launched in 2003 as a short-to-medium-term response to high unemployment.⁴⁹ The aim of the programme is to develop the skills of workers while on the job so as to increase their employability when they exit the programme.⁵⁰ The programme focuses on the creation of work opportunities through infrastructure delivery, using labour-intensive construction methods. EPWP is designed around service delivery projects that are needed, such as rural infrastructure, clearing of alien vegetation or community-based social services, such as early childhood or home community-based care.⁵¹ Its objective is to build, upgrade and maintain the social and economic infrastructure in all underdeveloped rural and urban areas that do have such infrastructure. An important element of the EPWP is that it is expected to employ local people to ensure that as they work they simultaneously acquire basic training and skills.⁵²

It is reported that 3.4 million work opportunities were created by March 2019 through the EPWP, one million of which are full-time equivalent jobs.⁵³ Research suggests that the programme has not been effective in poverty alleviation because it failed to target those with the highest unemployment rates.⁵⁴ Another criticism is that in most cases it provides temporary work, and participants become unemployed after a project terminates,⁵⁵ thereby creating a pool of skills for the country that cannot be absorbed in the workplace.

In conclusion, through the CRDP, NARYSEC, Agri-Parks and other initiatives in rural areas, 622 946 rural people were employed by March 2019 against the target of 924 140, which

⁴⁷ Damba (2015).

⁴⁸ DRDLR (2019b).

⁴⁹ Attman & Hemson (2007).

⁵⁰ Luka (2005).

⁵¹ Altman & Hemson (2007).

⁵² Luka (2005).

⁵³ DPME (2020).

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Luka (2005).

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means it was not fully, but partially achieved. Despite that, the major concern with the jobs created through all these programmes is that most of them are temporary, which means that participants return to unemployment after the projects have been completed. Further, there is a lack of coordination between all the departments providing services in rural areas.⁵⁶ As a result, there is duplication of work, creating uncertainty in the overall number of jobs created in rural areas, as there is no consolidated information.

The target on the number of rural people skilled was exceeded, as 595 777 rural people were trained in various skills development programmes by March 2019, including NARYSEC, against the target of 90 000.⁵⁷

vii. Summary of Progress on the Implementation of NDP

The implementation of the NDP during 2014 – 2019 period (MTSF) through the six priorities of Outcome 7 was badly performed. According to the DPME, of 39 targets, 18 (46%) were achieved while 19 (49%) were not achieved and the remaining two targets (5%) were not reported on.

3.4 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made to the Department of Agriculture, Rural Development and Land Reform for consideration:

- The Department should do all it can to ensure that land disbursed is used properly and effectively to gradually relieve South Africa from becoming a “*welfare state*” due to the burden carried by the Department of Social Development to provide livelihoods to poor rural families, when there is productive land being disbursed to rural communities.
- Since 21% of rural households continue to experience difficulty accessing food, these households must be targeted for provision of agricultural extension services, to ensure that redistributed land does not lie fallow while it is productive.
- The Department has only managed to utilise 763 715 hectares (76.3%) of one million hectares acquired by 2019. There is a need for the Department to still aim to meet these targets by speeding up the processes and addressing impediments.
- The Department needs to address the challenge of providing sustainable basic services to a dispersed population at reasonable cost in rural areas, as it relates to backlogs in key services, such as water, sanitation, electricity and roads. Since these key services are interlinked to improve rural areas, there must be targeted collaboration with the Departments of Public Works and Infrastructure, Water and Sanitation and Mineral Resources and Energy.
- To address poor capacity in local and district municipalities, the Department must seek collaboration with relevant Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) colleges and send rural youth to acquire technical skills, with a view to employing them to help these municipalities. The TVET collaboration would target skills to capacitate municipalities to deliver services towards rural development.

The following recommendations are made to Parliament:

⁵⁶DPME (2012).

⁵⁷ DRDLR (2019a).

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Through its various committees, Parliament can play a leading role to ensure that the various Government departments intensify their efforts towards the implementation of the NDP and thus reduce poverty, high unemployment and inequality in rural areas. In this regard, Parliament should:

- Intensify the political will to reduce poverty and unemployment in rural areas and ensure various departments fast-track the implementation of the NDP, especially chapter six, which deals with agriculture, land reform and rural development.
- Oversee the revision of the National Rural Youth Service Corps (NARYSEC) Programme in order to ensure training provided is in line with the mandate of the DALRRD.
- Use its oversight role to ensure that the DALRRD fast-tracks the pace of acquiring land for Previously Disadvantaged Individuals in line with the NDP. In particular, there is a need to review the role and function of the Office of the Valuer-General, which is meant to assist in accelerating land reform.
- Use its legislative mandate to expedite the processing of a legislative framework to allow for expropriation of land without compensation. The Comprehensive Rural Development Programme (CRDP) and other programmes initiated by the Department have made marginal contributions towards addressing poverty, unemployment and food insecurity in rural areas. It should be noted that the CRDP has been undermined by poor coordination within and across the three spheres of government; a lack of clear role clarification of stakeholders (in particular local government); poor community participation; and monitoring and evaluation. Parliament needs to monitor regularly the initiatives developed to address poverty in particular to create jobs, improve food security and access to basic services in rural areas (such as the CRDP, NARYSEC, land reform and the EPWP). The aim is to determine their effectiveness and impact, and ensure that the DALRRD has coordination structures in place to oversee all activities needed for effective rural development and provision of basic services in all three spheres of government.

3.5 Conclusion

Government has made some strides in addressing high levels of poverty and unemployment in rural areas through various strategies, programmes and initiatives. According to the 2014-2016 MTSF mid-term review report, South Africa was in a better place in 2017 than it was in 1994. Progress has been made towards realising the goals of the NDP, but progress is uneven across sectors.⁵⁸ In terms of land reform and rural development, significant progress has been made in addressing food insecurity and supporting rural enterprises, whilst the same cannot be said for job creation and providing basic services in rural areas. As a result, although there has been an improvement in the levels of poverty, unemployment and food insecurity, the situation remains worse in rural areas compared to urban areas. Therefore, there is still a lot that needs to be done in this area.

Finally, the comprehensive nature of poverty traps in the former Bantustans and challenges in farming regions means that only a multi-faceted development strategy, which is well financed and staffed, could significantly enhance economic activity, employment levels and living standards in rural areas. Therefore, all social partners need to work together to ensure the country is able to eliminate poverty, create jobs and employment opportunities for its people and a more equitable society.

⁵⁸ The Presidency (2017).

4. FISHERIES SECTOR

4.1 Introduction

The fisheries sector in South Africa is recognised globally in terms of its production and management. Fishing activities take place in marine and inland waters in the form of fish farming (aquaculture), wild capture and, to a lesser extent, culture/ranching fisheries. Wild capture fishery is composed of commercial, sport and recreational, and small-scale fisheries.⁵⁹ Commercial marine fisheries have 22 sectors that are more developed and have structured regulatory and legislative instruments, while inland capture fisheries are underdeveloped and have fragmented legal instruments. Sport and recreational fishing have approximately 2.5 million participants annually, translating into more than R18 billion contribution to the economy.⁶⁰ Marine commercial fishery employs between 23 000 and 26 000 people and contributes R8 billion to the economy (excluding inland fishery). On a nearly similar contribution, there are 22 000 marine small-scale fishers with an unknown economic contribution.⁶¹

In contrast, the number of participants and financial contribution of inland artisanal fishery is unknown. The total value of the fisheries sector is unidentified, including its socio-economic impact at the local, regional and national level. Despite this research and information gap, the fisheries sector directly employs people in harvesting, processing, marketing and distribution, and also contributes to employment-related services. These are the economic activities that the Government seeks to optimise and maximise its contribution to the long-term benefit of the country.⁶²

This section considers the implementation of the NDP in the fisheries sector during the 2014-2029 period. The application of fisheries policies and programmes contributes towards the long-term strategy that seeks to eliminate poverty, inequality and unemployment by 2030. This approach, therefore, needs to be kept in mind when evaluating fisheries policies and the allocation of fishing rights. The assessment of the fisheries sector is mainly against the set objectives and milestones.

4.2 Overview of the NDP for the Fisheries Sector

i. Diagnosis of prevailing challenges

During 2010, former President Jacob Zuma sought to establish a team of experts to conduct an assessment and diagnosis of various functions of the country and have a long-term vision of improving the lives of citizens. To this effect, he appointed the National Planning Commission consisting of 26 experts as part-time Commissioners to diagnose the country on a thematic approach, draft a vision statement for 2030, and pronounce on plans and measures to achieve the set vision through medium-term targets. In line with the mandate of the Commission, during June 2011, the Diagnostic Overview reports were released, which identified the main challenges confronting the country and examined their underlying causes. The five reports covered the following thematic areas: human conditions, material conditions, nation-building, the economy, and institutions and governance – the last of which is cross-cutting.

⁵⁹ DAFF (2016).

⁶⁰ Leibold and van Zyl (2008).

⁶¹ Department of Agriculture Forestry & Fisheries (2014; 2019).

⁶² Ginindza (2016a).

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The Diagnostic Reports highlighted the following nine key challenges:⁶³

- Too few South Africans, especially the youth, are employed.
- Although access to and participation in education has increased, the quality of education for poor black South Africans is sub-standard.
- Poorly located and inadequate infrastructure limits social inclusion and faster economic growth.
- Economic growth relies too much on the exploitation of natural resources and mineral endowments, which is not sustainable.
- Spatial challenges continue to marginalise the poor.
- The ailing public health system confronts a massive disease burden.
- The performance of the public service is uneven.
- The breakdown of accountability creates conditions in which corruption thrives, undermining state legitimacy and service delivery.
- South Africa remains a divided society, fuelling a cycle of mistrust and short-termism that undermines efforts to deal with the country's challenges. High levels of inequality compound these divisions and create fertile ground for crime. Crime, in turn, encourages the growth of gated communities, which generate a high degree of relational distance, undermining the opportunity for social compacts.

These diagnostic findings have a direct bearing on the coastal fishing communities and the sector in its entirety. All these identified challenges are experienced in the coastal towns and villages or where they live closer to fishing water bodies.

ii. National Development Plan

The NDP recognises the importance of the fisheries sector within the context of maritime economic potential. The discussions are located primarily within the confines of sustainable natural resource use. As such, scientific research and monitoring on fisheries resources are primed to be of utmost importance to achieve sustainable fisheries resource use. The NDP further recognises the importance of small-scale and artisanal fishing. However, it does not regard small-scale fisheries as a vehicle to address poverty and unemployment, mainly due to the limited fisheries resources. The NDP discourages increasing the number of participants in the small-scale fisheries sector because it reduces the net gain per participant and increases the difficulty of law enforcement. The NDP encourages research into new fisheries to expand opportunities.⁶⁴

The NDP considers fishing rights allocation and sustainable exploitation of fisheries resources as viable tools for the transformation of the fisheries sector. This approach has the potential to eliminate poverty, inequality and unemployment. Two chapters in the NDP directly affect the fisheries sector, while other sections affect it indirectly. Therefore, the overview contained in this document is limited to the two areas, namely inclusive rural development and environmental sustainability.

⁶³ National Planning Commission (2011).

⁶⁴ Ibid.

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1. Vision 2030 for an integrated and inclusive rural economy

By 2030, South Africa's remote areas should have greater participation in the economic, social and political landscape of the country, with access to quality essential services. The vision includes better integration, which can be achieved through land reform and poverty alleviation, with expansion in irrigated agriculture being the driving force. The support of human capital will be gained through the use of essential services in health, quality education and social security. Access to vital social and infrastructural facilities is a high priority for many rural households.

The NDP advocates for the transformation of the fisheries sector in terms of ownership and economic contribution through viable fishing rights, support in farms and sustainable exploitation of resources. Given the fundamental issues, the NDP acknowledges that the fishing sector is relatively transformed, but fishing activities are not inclusive. Furthermore, the NDP cautions against issuing many fishing rights of low value, as it lowers the average gain per fisher and could be ineffective in fighting poverty and non-compliance among fishers. In industrial fishing, the NDP is against taking fishing rights away from industrial fishers in favour of small-scale fishers because this is perceived to threaten jobs. Fisheries research and active monitoring systems are considered as of paramount importance to ensure a viable and sustainable fishery. The NDP recommends that alternative economic opportunities be made available to supplement livelihoods of fishing communities and that fisheries policies seek to maximise sustainable employment and advocate for allocation of viable fishing rights.⁶⁵

The former Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries responded to the NDP with plans to support aquaculture investment and production, and creation of jobs through the Expanded Public Works Programme (EPWP). It is the view of the Department that re-building fish stocks will go a long way in growing the fisheries sector. Associated projects involve the revitalisation of State-owned hatcheries, sustainable land use, and allocation of commercial fishing rights to promote participation in the South African fisheries. Also in line with the NDP recommendation of accessibility of Government service, the Department plans to advance the e-permitting service and the decentralisation of its services for coastal provinces, including inland provinces for aquaculture. References to the e-permitting service and decentralisation is not new, but never had timelines attached to its completion.

2. Vision 2030 for environmental sustainability

South Africa has reduced its dependency on carbon, natural resources and energy while balancing this transition with its objectives of increasing employment and reducing inequality. Development initiatives, especially in rural communities, are increasingly resilient to the impact of climate change, with mutual benefits between sustainable development and low-carbon growth quickly identified and exploited. The State has significantly strengthened its capacity to manage the ongoing internalisation of environmental costs and to respond to the increasingly severe impacts of climate change.

⁶⁵ National Planning Commission (2011).

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4.3 Progress on the implementation of NDP

Government departments had to develop and align sector-specific programmes and activities that will contribute towards the 2030 goals. Most importantly, each sector had to develop short and medium-term goals that would cumulatively add to the larger goal. During the 2014-2019 period, the MTSF was the overarching guide in the development and implementation of outcome-driven plans. During the same time, the former Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries Department developed the Agriculture Policy Action Plan to aid the implementation of plans towards the NDP. One of the central and cross-sectoral programmes was the introduction of Operation Phakisa for the marine environment that was later expanded to include other sectors. The following section will highlight the contribution of these essential policy plans towards the goals of the NDP.

One of the matters identified in the NDP is the development of economic opportunities in the value chain to expand the economic impact of the fisheries sector. The main stumbling block had been the non-existing or fragmented inland fisheries legislation. This fragmentation affects the wild capture, aquaculture and the potential for culture fisheries. Although there was a presidential pronouncement before Cabinet restructuring to put all food production sectors under agriculture, Government was slow in the implementation of this directive. The argument had been that fish farming and stock enhancement belong in the husbandry and propagation of animals, as opposed to being treated as a conservation matter. This argument seems to have failed, as manifested in the 2019 Cabinet restructuring that split fish farming from other agricultural activities.

MTSF 2014 – 2019

As mentioned above, the MTSF⁶⁶, 2014 – 2019 was developed as the Government's strategic plan for the 2014-2019 electoral term. It reflects national priorities, including the commitment to implement the NDP, and highlights Government's support for a competitive economy, creation of decent work opportunities and encouragement of investment. The MTSF sets out the actions Government will take and targets to be achieved. It also provides a framework for the other plans of national, provincial and local government. The Department contributed to three of the 14 national outcomes over the MTSF for 2014-2019, as articulated in the Annual Performance Plans and the Annual Reports for the period under review. The specific outcomes and targets that impact the fisheries sector are:

- Outcome 4 - Decent Employment through inclusive growth;
- Outcome 7 - Vibrant, equitable and sustainable rural communities contributing towards food security for all; and
- Outcome 10 - Protect and enhance our environmental assets and natural resources.

The contributions to these outcomes were largely collaborative with other departments, such as Rural Development and Land Reform; Finance; Economic Development; Trade and Industry; Science and Technology; Public Enterprises; Higher Education and Training; Environmental Affairs; Planning Monitoring and Evaluation; Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs; Social Development; Small Business Development; Water and Sanitation; Human Settlements; Provincial departments; and some municipalities. In some

⁶⁶ The Presidency. (2014).

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instances, the Department played a leading role, while in other cases it played a supporting role.

i Outcome 4: Decent employment through inclusive growth

The infrastructure build programme was identified as a productive investment that would drive job creation. There was no set target for decent employment in 2014, so it is difficult to assess whether the target was achieved or not. The collaborative work of the departments saw the upgrade of 12 fishing harbours, 11 of which are located in the Western Cape Province. Some harbours are not fully completed and are running beyond scheduled plans and budgets. In some respects, administrative requirements and legal matters caused delays in the implementation of infrastructure upgrades. The infrastructure upgrades accounted for a growing share of employment, workers' education and skills. Economic opportunities for historically excluded and vulnerable groups were expanded, and the growth and development in small business and cooperatives were improved markedly. Some of these skills and jobs happened during upgrades of harbours wherein local community members received training and certificates in various economically essential skills, such as welding, diving and skipper courses. The public employment schemes provided much-needed relief for the unemployed under the different guises of the Expanded Public Works Programmes implemented by the Department.

Another outcome that has been difficult to assess relates to conflict resolution in the workplace. The annual reports do account for some progress; however, there was no target in the first place, which complicates a proper assessment of progress. As a result, some cases are still pending and are yet to be concluded. Some news coverage had indicated an increase in labour protests during this period, including both government and private sectors. The main grievance had consistently related to wage and salary increases. Ministers had committed to reducing the number of enrolled grievances and protests, and ensuring collaboration between Government, organised business and organised labour for improved working conditions.

ii Outcome 7: Vibrant, equitable, sustainable rural communities contributing towards food security for all

The collaborative work between the Departments of Rural Development and Land Reform; Agriculture; and Water and Sanitation was expected to improve land administration and spatial planning for integrated development in rural areas. Progress has been slow, in that freshwater aquaculture has remained hamstrung by bureaucratic processes to access land and water. Small-scale fishing communities have remained constrained in the state of food and nutrition insecurity. The situation was exacerbated by the failure of the Department to allocate fishing rights to the *bona fide* fishers following the 2007 Equality Court judgement.⁶⁷ The sound implementation of the small-scale fisheries policy is expected to improve access to fish for food and livelihood, thus reducing food and nutrition insecurity in many coastal communities that depend or had traditionally depended on fisheries resources. Support to small-scale fishers and fishing SMMEs has not been forthcoming over the years, despite numerous ministerial pronouncements and promises. The expected development and support (technical, financial, infrastructure) is geared towards achieving some sectoral transformation. The disparity has been that Government prioritised the allocation of fishing

⁶⁷ Equality Court (2007).

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rights to the commercial fishing sectors over the small-scale fishers. In comparative terms, commercial fishing has had two cycles of fishing rights allocations while small-scale fishers are yet to receive fishing rights. This disparity has also impaired the growth of sustainable rural enterprises and industries that have the potential to create jobs.

iii Outcome 10: Protect and enhance our environmental assets and natural resources

The 2018 National Biodiversity Assessment Report⁶⁸ indicates that the ecosystems face resource utilisation pressures. The pressures on freshwater fish have resulted in several localised extinctions. However, active management interventions by conservation agencies, targeted at Critically Endangered species, have prevented any species extinctions taking place. The combination of pressures are linked to water abstraction and flow regulation, pollution, overfishing (especially gillnetting), and predation by invasive species. More than 63% of the estuarine area is heavily or critically modified with critical ecological processes under severe pressure, which reduces productivity, food security, fisheries livelihoods, property values and recreational enjoyment. The main pressures impacting marine ecosystems and species include fishing, freshwater flow reduction, coastal development (including ports and harbours), pollution and climate change. South African ocean activities are expanding and diversifying as South Africa develops its ocean economy. Approximately half of the marine ecosystem types are threatened; by area, this equates to only 5% of the ocean space around South Africa, with more inshore and shelf ecosystem types threatened than those in the slope and abyss. Fisheries stock status is not assessed for 90% of the 770 marine species that fishers harvest. Of the assessed resources, more than a third are over-exploited or collapsed. Emerging pressures include increasing pollution concerns, desalination and ocean noise. A total of 96 introduced marine species, 55 of which are invasive, have been reported. Climate change causes changes in currents, upwelling, water temperatures and turbidity, while elevated atmospheric carbon dioxide results in increasing ocean acidification.

Operation Phakisa

Former President Jacob Zuma, together with other delegates, embarked on a State visit during August 2013 to Malaysia. The Malaysian Government briefed the South African delegation on their programme, the Big Fast Results Methodology, used as a vehicle to achieve significant government and economic transformation within a very short time. The programme addressed Government challenges such as poverty, crime and unemployment. The South African delegation was impressed and sought to domesticate the programme in the South African setting. The Malaysian Government assisted the South African Government to adapt the programme to address South African challenges. The South African version was named Operation Phakisa. Operation Phakisa was officially launched in July 2014 as a vehicle to achieve the ideals articulated in the NDP, such as boosting economic growth, job creation and reducing inequality.⁶⁹ Operation Phakisa entails first conducting a detailed problem analysis, followed by setting priorities, the required intervention, planning, delivery, and ongoing monitoring of progress towards the set goals. South Africa is targeting the oceans economy, as it is one of the key drivers in the Nine-

⁶⁸ South African National Biodiversity Institute (2019).

⁶⁹ The Presidency & Invest SA (2016)

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Point Plan to grow the economy, create jobs, transform the economy and attract investment.⁷⁰

Aquaculture

The Aquaculture Lab, the group responsible for the aquaculture focus area of Operation Phakisa, undertook the task of unlocking the potential of the aquaculture sector in South Africa. The goal is to grow Aquaculture to play a major role in the supply of fish products, and an enhanced role in job creation and contribution to national income. South Africa's aquaculture sector has high growth potential due to increasing demand for fish in the face of declining fish stocks in the ocean and South Africa's abundance of marine and freshwater resources. The sector also offers significant potential for rural development, especially for the marginalised coastal communities. The Aquaculture Lab aims to grow sector revenue from R0.67 billion to R3 billion; production by 20 000 tonnes; jobs from 2 227 to 15 000 and to ensure increased participation to support transformation in the sector by 2019.⁷¹ The April 2018 report from the Department of Environmental Affairs (Oceans Economy Secretariat) seems to suggest that the targets have been revised upwards. For example, the target economic contribution from the aquaculture and fisheries sector is now set at R10-16 billion, while jobs is set at between 170 000 and 250 000.⁷²

The Aquaculture Lab identified eight key initiatives, which are expected to spur the growth of the sector. One such initiative will address the selection and implementation of 24 projects, improving both the number and productivity of the new farms. Three initiatives relate to the creation of an enabling regulatory environment, and others focus on funding support, increasing the skills pool and awareness and improving access to markets. To deliver on these initiatives, the Aquaculture Lab created detailed implementation plans and accompanying budgets, a proposed governance system to take responsibility for initiatives and key performance indicators to help monitor delivery. The implementation is already underway, as some projects were already ongoing in response to other policies. The Department has been actively approaching all regulatory bodies involved in aquaculture to develop a sole and standardised process of governing aquaculture activities. To this end, the Aquaculture Development Bill [B22-2018] was developed, widely consulted on, and finally tabled in Parliament in June 2018 as a Section 76 (Ordinary Bill affecting the provinces). The Bill lapsed and is due for re-introduction during the 2020/2021 financial year.

The aquaculture sector is still small and faces several challenges. Production is focused on a few high-value species, such as abalone, oysters, mussels, finfish and trout – driven mainly by the high cost of production. Other challenges include regulatory barriers, difficulty in accessing funding, poor access to markets, limited pool of skills, poor access to quality inputs, fragmented research and development, limited infrastructure in rural areas and inclusivity in the sector.⁷³ The targets were arguably too ambitious and, for the most part, unrealistic under the economic conditions that prevailed during the period under review. The jobs, economic contribution and required skills were not realised because all contributions are far below the set targets. For example, created jobs are still below 3 000, production

⁷⁰ The Presidency. (2016); Zuma JG. (2017); The Presidency, Invest SA (2016).

⁷¹ The Presidency (2014).

⁷² Share (2018).

⁷³ The Presidency (2014); Share (2016; 2018).

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below 7 000 tonnes, while skills development is ongoing, with students still at universities. One of the driving factors had been the lack of funds to realise all the Phakisa plans. Government departments were expected to reprioritise their existing budgets and, where possible, channel resources towards the Phakisa objectives. The Department ended the period under review mentioning that the Phakisa plan was an unfunded mandate; hence it could not be implemented as planned. Timelines had to be revised and extended by a further 12 years. The goals that were initially supposed to be achieved by 2019 were reviewed by 2016 to 2030, then again by 2018 to 2032. Most importantly, the aquaculture projects were focused in the Western Cape, while other provinces received less attention, in particular rural regions.

Figure 1. Location of the original aquaculture projects under Operation Phakisa (Aquaculture).⁷⁴

⁷⁴ Share (2018)

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Figure 2. Location of the new 17 aquaculture projects under operation Phakisa (Aquaculture)⁷⁵

The Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) reports that it is contributing towards Ocean Phakisa through its flagship funding mechanism - the Aquaculture Development and Enhancement Programme (ADEP). The ADEP is an incentive programme available to South African-registered entities engaged in primary, secondary and ancillary aquaculture activities in both marine and freshwater classified under SIC 132 (fish hatcheries and fish farms) and SIC 301 and 302 (production, processing and preserving of aquaculture fish). The grant is provided directly to approved applications for new, upgrading or expansion projects. The ADEP, which issued its first approvals in March 2013, was designed to encourage the geographic spread of aquaculture development beyond the established Western Cape region. ADEP has somewhat achieved this objective with approved projects valued at R254 million in Gauteng, Mpumalanga, KwaZulu-Natal, North West and Limpopo. The DTI has partnered with the National Metrology Institute of South Africa (NMISA) to develop standards for aquaculture and fisheries food and food products, some of which include abalone, fish oil, frozen rock lobster and frozen lobster products, canned fisheries products, and raw fisheries products. There are no tangible outcomes as yet on the adoption and implementation of the standards in the sector, mainly because farmers are still focused on trying to get consistent production.

*Small harbours*⁷⁶

The South African coastline has 13 proclaimed fishing harbours, with 12 located in the Western Cape and one in the Eastern Cape. There are also approximately 50 potential and existing unproclaimed harbours in the Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, Northern Cape and Western Cape. The small harbours (proclaimed and unproclaimed) have a significant role to play in the socio-economic development of the communities where they are located and

⁷⁵ Share (2018).

⁷⁶ Ginindza (2016a); Share (2016); The DTI (2016).

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could contribute to growing the bigger maritime economy. Despite their socio-economic significance, small harbours are also critical in maintaining security and territorial integrity of the country, as these harbours constitute part of the borders of the Republic. Harbours have been identified as candidates of the Strategic Infrastructure Projects (SIP) under the Presidential Infrastructure Coordinating Commission.

The current realities are that the infrastructure of small harbours is in a state of disrepair, lack of maintenance, safety, security measures and almost non-existent management. For example, some small harbours have become a hive of all sorts of crimes, such as landing of poached fisheries resources, drug trade and prostitution. The lack of investment and cohesive legislative and regulatory framework creates a conducive environment for criminal elements to thrive. The absence of a dedicated small harbour management authority impairs plans for small harbour development.

Under the custodianship of the Department of Public Works and DAFF, R6 billion was reportedly allocated over the MTEF for repairs, upgrades, dredging of harbour basins and removal of sunken boats. This investment is expected to create at least 12 100 jobs in the various small towns closer to the earmarked small harbours. Further plans include the establishment of a small harbours development unit, the proclamation of new small harbours and investment in harbour infrastructure to support tourism and aquaculture. Whilst very little progress has been made, plans are underway to develop detailed implementation plans for small harbours infrastructure re-development/development and proclamation of three new small harbours.

*Marine protection services and ocean governance*⁷⁷

Marine environmental governance in South Africa is currently undertaken in a sectoral fashion. The DEA is generally responsible for overarching environmental governance, while the responsibility for sectoral environmental management is devolved to the economic departments, notably the Department of Mineral Resources (DMR), Department of Energy (DOE), DAFF, and DOT. An integrated approach to ocean governance is possible if a single regulatory agency is tasked with all decision-making over human use activity in South Africa's oceans. Various maritime nations have attempted such an approach, but it has generally proved impossible to implement, largely because it is difficult to persuade state organs to cede their regulatory powers to a new structure.

The current arrangements complicate maritime governance and results in uncertainty of roles and responsibilities. The absence of a single institutional framework negates the good intentions among some departments, as manifested by poor coordination and weak enforcement. The results of weak or poor coordination has seen illegal, unregulated and unreported (IUU) fishing practices getting established in areas that had traditionally been excluded. The lack of human and financial resources puts the maritime territory at risk of being exploited without control. Furthermore, there is minimal compliance monitoring and surveys in the oceans. There is a big research and knowledge gap, mainly as a result of working in silos among departments and not sharing information. The discussion that Parliament should have should focus on resolving these working in silo approaches that have proven to be a failure.

⁷⁷ Ginindza (2016b); Janse van Rensburg *et al* (2016).

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The socio-economic costs of illegal, unregulated and unreported fishing are vast, although they cannot be accurately quantified because perpetrators apply complex, dynamic and evolving strategies to evade detection or being dismantled. A 2009 study that tried to quantify the value of fish that is illegally caught and exported from South Africa's major commercial fisheries estimated the catches to be worth R6 billion (US\$790 million), of which R4.4 billion was contributed by the abalone and Patagonian toothfish.⁷⁸ This value is equivalent to the value of legally caught fish from the 17 commercial fisheries. South Africa is considered to be a source, transit, and destination country for men, women, and children subjected to forced labour and sex trafficking. While the majority of trafficking victims in South Africa are labour trafficking victims, through land and air borders, there are reports of human trafficking from marine fishing and transport operations.

It is envisaged that Operation Phakisa and the ongoing development of the National Maritime Security Strategy by the Department of Transport will contribute significantly towards harmonising and fostering effective and efficient maritime security. Furthermore, the Border Management Agency Bill, passed by the National Assembly in June 2017, was under consideration by the National Council of Provinces in 2019. The Bill was passed by the National Assembly during March 2020. The Bill is expected to usher in a new season where the process of seeking approval will be rid of bureaucracy, as better command and control systems will be introduced. Furthermore, it will also ease the flow of information when requests for joint operations are put forward, instead of the current arrangement where intelligence is shared at the time of implementation. The currently outdated databases will likely be an issue of the past when all maritime databases are upgraded and integrated to ensure that all parties have real-time access to authorised fishing vessels, fishing rights and permits.

The South African Department of Defence has, through Armscor, placed an order for three Inshore Patrol Vessels (IPV), 62 x 11 metres as part of Operation Phakisa from the Damen Shipyards Cape Town (Damen). The vessels form part of the South African Navy's Project Biro. The project aims to develop South Africa's maritime security, ensuring that the country has the capability to respond effectively, rapidly and cost-efficiently to maritime threats such as illegal trafficking and fishing.⁷⁹ This move by the Navy may already be seen as usurping the Department's mandate of addressing illegal fishing. This move could also be seen as a welcome resource injection at a time when the only three fisheries patrol vessels are unable to patrol the 3000 km coast. During the period under review, there were few incidents of illegal fishing within the South African EEZ where the Department only managed to apprehend a fraction of illegal fishing vessels from foreign countries. The Department is unable to correctly estimate the volumes and value of poached resources because they struggle to arrest illegal fishers.

Sustainable fisheries resources use

Commercial marine fisheries has 22 sectors that are more developed and have structured regulatory and legislative instruments, while inland capture fisheries are underdeveloped and have fragmented legal instruments. The sustainable use of the fisheries resources, both inland and marine, require consistent investment in research, development and innovation support. It is only through such inputs that the potential of the fisheries sector could translate

⁷⁸ Gosling (2009).

⁷⁹ Damen (2018).

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into the envisaged inclusive growth by enhancing the productivity of existing and emerging enterprises and supporting the development of new industries. Value addition have proven in some jurisdictions to reduce the need for catching high volumes of fish to achieve business sustainability. Value addition could significantly improve the livelihoods of the fishers and their fishing enterprises while allowing the fisheries resources an opportunity to recover and expand.

During 2019, the South African Government finalised 22 additional Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) within South Africa's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) through the rollout of Operation Phakisa. These additional MPAs have been designed to protect important marine ecosystems and habitats that are necessary to ensure the sustainability of South Africa's marine living resources. Each MPA has set management objectives, and collectively they will increase South Africa's formally protected ocean space from 0.5 per cent to 5 per cent by 2033 (revised from 2030).

It is also worth mentioning that some of the Operation Phakisa plans seem to be clashing in areas of overlap and remains unresolved, at least to the Committee. For example, there are plans for mining and exploration of oil and gas reserves in the oceans on or near fishing grounds. Additionally, the Department of Environmental Affairs has expanded the network of MPAs by adding 22 new MPAs effective from October 2019 as part of the Operation Phakisa Initiative and its National Protected Area Expansion Strategy. The Department has gazetted the regulations declaring Bettys Bay, Robberg and Goukamma Marine Protected Area under section 22 of the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act No. 57 of 2003. Some of the areas are known fishing grounds for commercial and small-scale fishers.

At Betty's Bay the aim is to protect abalone, West Coast rock lobster and linefish species by zoning the MPA as a single restricted zone where fishing is completely prohibited. At the Goukamma MPA the aim is to create two restricted zones and one controlled zone where only fishing from the shore is allowed to allow linefish species to recover. At the Robberg MPA there will be two types of zones in the MPA, a restricted zone where no fishing may occur, and three controlled zones where only recreational shore-angling can take place. It is DEA's view that excluding subsistence fishers and only allowing recreational fishers will enhance the fisheries and conservation benefits of the MPA. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that these species are earmarked for inclusion in the basket of species to be fished by small-scale fishers.

The outcomes of establishing MPAs vary among the different places along the four coastal provinces. The issues range from the recovery of fish stock to the social well-being of the communities adjacent to the MPAs and Government's ability to implement, monitor and address arising challenges adequately. Recent studies have found in some places the linefish stocks recovering well, thus advancing the argument of establishing even more MPAs. In some situations, the lack of capacity from Government to implement and oversee the MPAs has led to a new discussion of avoiding such failures in the future where MPAs will be established, and their management will be business as usual. In some regions, the species are overfished to such an extent that they are on the verge of being economically extinct or justifying the proposals for the closure of the fisheries.⁸⁰

⁸⁰ Lombard et al (2019); South African National Biodiversity Institute (2019).

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4.4 Progress on the Implementation of NDP between 2014 and 2019

Table 10: Progress on implementation of fisheries priorities

Priorities/Sub-outcome	2014 Baseline	2019 Key Targets	Progress by March 2019 ⁸¹
Development and transformation of the inland fisheries sector	Inland fisheries policy fragmented and managed under provinces	National policy and legislation to manage access to dams and their fishery resources	Draft Inland Fisheries Policy undergoing internal consultations
Development of economic opportunities in the fisheries value chain	None	Fish processing facilities for small-scale fishers	None so far. It will begin after fishing rights are allocated.
Decent employment through inclusive growth	There was no baseline for the fisheries sector	1 million jobs in agriculture, forestry and fisheries (not broken down to each sector)	Unknown for the fisheries sector, but short-term jobs were created under the EPWP and harbour projects
Sustainable rural communities	Interim Relief Programme	Allocation of small-scale fishing rights	The allocation of small-scale fishing rights was only starting.
Sustainable use of natural resources	50% of stocks are considered to be of concern (orange and red groups)	Conservation, protection, rehabilitation and recovery of depleted and degraded natural resources	48% of stocks are considered to be of concern (orange and red groups)
Lead and coordinate government food security initiatives	Fishing Rights Allocation Process (FRAP) 2013	Equitable and orderly access to the marine living resources by 2019/20	Fishing rights were only allocated to the commercial fishing sector
Conservation, protection, rehabilitation and recovery of depleted and degraded natural resources	Compliance and enforcement in priority fisheries	Law enforcement and implementation of fish stock recovery plans	Fisheries patrols and inspections have been a success, however, fish stocks are not recovering as anticipated, and more inshore and shelf ecosystem types are threatened
Increase the economic contribution of the aquaculture sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R0.67 billion revenue • 6 000 tonnes production • 2 227 jobs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R3 billion revenue • 20 000 tonnes production • 15 000 jobs 	None of the targets were achieved, instead the target date was extended to 2032

4.5 Recommendations

Most of Government's plans in the fisheries sectors were not fully achieved as they relate to the objectives aligned to the NDP. The parliamentary committees should intensify their efforts in conducting oversight and stakeholder engagements to ensure implementation of programmes geared towards the reduction of poverty, unemployment and inequality in communities along water bodies.

⁸¹ Targets highlighted in red indicate targets that are not achieved while those highlighted in green are achieved.

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In this regard, Parliament should use its oversight role to ensure that the relevant Departments:

- Set clear transformation targets for the fisheries sector in terms of ownership and economic contribution through fishing rights allocation, job creation and sustainable exploitation of fisheries resources.
- Avoid issuing many fishing rights of low value, as this lowers the average gain per fisher and could be ineffective in fighting poverty and non-compliance among fishers.
- Create support vehicles in favour of small-scale fishers to sustain operations and create jobs.
- Allocate resources towards fisheries research and development, and develop effective monitoring systems to ensure a viable and sustainable fishery.
- Create alternative economic opportunities to supplement livelihoods of fishing communities, such as agro-processing, tourism, fisheries and small enterprises where the potential exists.
- Ensure that its fisheries policies maximise sustainable employment and advocate for the allocation of viable fishing rights in all fishing sectors.
- Make available support for new entrants in the entire value chain of the fishing sector, including market linkages.
- Develop and implement programmes to support food security through increased intake of fish, fruit and vegetables and reduce intake of saturated fats, sugar and salt.
- Develop practical programmes to strengthen the resilience of society and the economy, while developing and implementing ways of protecting the most vulnerable.
- Review existing programmes that conserve water, reduce pollution, enhance food production and safety, and rebuild depleted fishing stocks.
- Along with sectors players, invest in mitigation and adaptation technologies and research into the conservation and rehabilitation of ecosystems and biodiversity assets.
- Explore fish stock enhancement approaches to improve dwindling or endangered fisheries resources.

Responsible departments should be Environment, Forestry and Fisheries (lead department), Science and Technology, Defence (South African Navy), Safety and Security, Trade and Industry, and Department of Environmental Affairs.

4.6 Conclusion

Aquaculture has a long history of being viewed as a viable alternative to unstable capture fisheries. The aquaculture sector is still small, however, contributes towards valuable employment in some regions. Both the capture and aquaculture sectors of the fisheries industry require specific research and management interventions to be sustainable. Promoting aquaculture could relieve the pressure on wild fish stocks and create an opportunity to meet the growing demand for fish. It will also create new economic opportunities in the fishing industry. The main challenge facing the country is to create a balance between optimising the social and economic potential of the sector while protecting the integrity of the marine and coastal systems. Parliament will, therefore, have to play a more hands-on role in its oversight to ensure the implementation of set targets within the available resources. Most importantly, there should be a balance between plans and the capacity to deliver to avoid the mismatch that was observed during the 2014-2019 implementation period.

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Chapter 6 of the NDP envisions rural areas that are spatially, socially and economically well well-integrated, where residents have economic growth, food security and jobs, as well as improved access to basic essential services, healthcare and public transport. It envisages that by 2030 Agriculture will create close to one million new jobs, contributing significantly to reducing overall unemployment. The question is, since the first phase of the NDP implementation (i.e. 2014-2019 MTSF) has passed, what progress has been made towards these goals? While the agricultural sector is at the forefront of job creation in terms of the NDP, it is currently under strain because of high input costs, political uncertainty, global price volatility, climate change and stressed farmers. Since the 2016/17 drought, the agricultural sector has shrunk in its contribution to the GDP and shed jobs. It is an accepted fact in development economics that agriculture usually shrinks as economies develop (through structural transformation). In South Africa, however, there is still potential for job growth. Rural employment could grow with reformed land tenure, support to farmers, expanded social services, higher agricultural output, mining social investment and tourism. The discussion above shows that the Government has made some strides in addressing high levels of poverty and unemployment in rural areas through various strategies, programmes and initiatives. Progress has been made towards realising the goals of the NDP, but progress is uneven across sectors.

In terms of land reform and rural development, significant progress has been made in addressing food insecurity and supporting rural enterprises. In contrast, Government has not done well in terms of job creation and providing basic essential services in rural areas. As a result, although there has been an improvement in the levels of poverty, unemployment and food insecurity, the situation remains worse in rural areas compared to urban areas. Therefore, there is still a lot that needs to be done in this area.

Although the contribution of the fisheries sector to an integrated and inclusive rural economy could be advanced to transform the historical patterns of ownership and economic participation, the failure of the former DAFF to amend the Marine Living Resources Act to address observed weaknesses in the transformation of fisheries, such as fronting and armchair fishers, meant that it did not make the required contribution. In addition, since small-scale fishing rights were not allocated during the 2014-2019 period, there is no positive outcome on employment and sustainable rural communities contributing towards food security for all fishing rights. Therefore, there is a need re-organise commercial fishing rights allocations to accommodate small-scale fishers while bearing in mind the perceived threats to jobs for commercial fishers. There is also a need to intensify fisheries research and active monitoring systems, as they are considered of paramount importance to ensure a viable and sustainable fishery to create sustainable employment in the sector.

In general, though progress has been made towards realising the goals of the NDP, across the economic, social services and governance sectors, progress is uneven across sectors. This could possibly be ascribed to the fact that there are too many government priorities that are accorded equal weighting and status, which led slow/poor implementation of the NDP. As a result, resources are thinly spread, given the current economic environment. Therefore, the NDP needs to be aligned to the country's budgetary commitments, or else it will not live up to all it promises. For the NDP proposals to materialise, the country's priority-setting needs to focus succinctly on drivers of economic development in order to pursue the goal of inclusive economic growth.

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Furthermore, performance on NDP 2030 actions, which require cooperation across multiple departments, spheres of government or non-governmental stakeholders shows unsatisfactory implementation progress. In particular, the comprehensive nature of poverty traps in the former Bantustans and challenges in farming regions means that only a multi-faceted development strategy, which is well well-financed and staffed, could significantly enhance rural economic activity, employment levels and living standards in rural areas. Therefore, all social partners need to work together to ensure the country is able to eliminate poverty, create jobs and employment opportunities for its people and to create a more equitable society. Most importantly, there should be a balance between plans and the capacity to deliver to avoid the mismatch that was observed during the 2014-2019 implementation period.

It is recommended in this document that through its legislative and oversight mandate, Parliament should play a leading role to ensure that the various Government departments intensify their efforts towards the implementation of the NDP in a bid to reduce poverty, high unemployment and inequality, especially in rural areas. In particular, Parliament should:

- Monitor regularly the initiatives developed to address poverty, in particular to create jobs, improve food security and access to basic services in rural areas in order to determine their effectiveness and impact, and to ensure that the DALRRD has coordination structures in place to oversee all activities needed for effective rural development and provision of basic services in all three spheres of Government.
- Monitor support provided by the DALRRD to smallholder farmers to ensure that tailor-made support packages for targeted market-oriented smallholder farmers in an expanded land reform programme are implemented, as this is key to creating large numbers of new employment opportunities.
- Oversee the transformation of the fisheries sector in terms of ownership and economic contribution through fishing rights allocation and sustainable exploitation of fisheries resources in order to maximise sustainable employment in the sector and improve food security through the review of fisheries policies.

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